

MODELS FOR IMPACT

OF CURRENTS ON NEOCORTICAL TISSUE AND NEURODYNAMICS
HIVE DELIVERABLE D1.3

F. WENDLING
I. MERLET
B. MOLAE-ARDEKANI

hiVE
HYPER
INTERACTION
VIABILITY
EXPERIMENTS

HIVE: Hyper Interaction Viability Experiments

EU FP7 FET OPEN - 222079

WorkPackage WP1: Biophysical models of stimulation

**Deliverable D1.3:
Models for impact of current on neocortical tissue
and brain neurodynamics**

Fabrice WENDLING, Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale (INSERM)

Isabelle MERLET, INSERM

Behnam MOLAEI-ARDEKANI, INSERM

Release date: 20 August, 2009

Status: public/confidential

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this report, we present the progress accomplished during the first year of the HIVE project in the development of computational models describing the impact of current on neocortical tissue (local level) and on brain neurodynamics (global level).

This report is organized according to two main sections. The first one is devoted to physiologically-plausible models of neuronal assemblies of the cerebral cortex (local level). The second one describes the strategy we defined for the development of a model describing the neurodynamics of the human brain (global level).

As far as the impact of currents at local level is concerned, a neural mass model was developed based on a literature review about the cyto-architecture of the cerebral cortex. In this model, we studied a first scenario according to which the electrical stimulation only affects the main cells (pyramidal neurons). For this scenario, we identified some necessary conditions in this model to reproduce the real signals recorded in rabbits by UPO (WP2). We found some model configurations that lead to the simulation of signals resembling actual responses. Although it is still at an early stage, we think that the model could provide insights about: i) the respective contribution of the subpopulations of cells to the evoked response, ii) the effect of the stimulation on main cells and on interneurons and iii) the interpretation of real responses with respect to stimulation parameters. Therefore, this model should contribute to a major issue of HIVE: the better understanding of the response of cortical circuits to externally-applied electric field induced by direct stimulation of the cortex.

Regarding the perspectives on this part of the work, these preliminary results should be confirmed by means of real data recorded in the cerebral cortex *in vivo*. In particular, a characterization of cortical responses (positive and negative peaks, amplitude and corresponding latencies) as a function of stimulation parameters is required. This characterization will be used to validate the simulation results. Another perspective is to test experimentally some model predictions by selective blockade of synaptic receptors, for instance.

As far as the modeling of global neurodynamics in the human brain is concerned, we have defined a strategy based on the extension of a model previously published by Inserm. The novelty is to now account for the main neocortical regions in the human brain and for the connectivity among these regions. Indeed, some recently published data (referred to as the “human connectome”) provide a solid basis to represent realistic anatomo-functional aspects in the global model to be developed.

From this model, our perspective is to solve the EEG forward problem (as opposed to the inverse problem) in order to simulate electrical potentials recorded at the scalp level. As the activity of simulated neocortical sources can be modulated by externally-applied electric fields, the model should predict some changes occurring in the EEG in response to stimulation. This is also a major issue of HIVE: the better understanding of the interaction between the brain activity (as reflected in the EEG) and electric fields induced by tDCS or TMS.

In this report, interactions with other participants (mainly Starlab, FFCUL and UPO at this stage of the work) are systematically highlighted using light grey boxes. This will help the reader to better identify the links between workpackages (mainly between WP1 and WP2 at this stage) and between the contributions of the different partners (Starlab, FFCUL, UPO and INSERM).

Deliverable Identification Sheet

IST Project No.	FP7 – FET OPEN – 222079
Acronym	HIVE
Full title	Hyper Interaction Viability Experiments
Project URL	http://www.hive-eu.org/
EU Project Officer	Aymard De-Touzalin

Deliverable	D1.3 Models for impact of current on neocortical tissue and brain neurodynamics
Work package	WP1 Biophysical models of stimulation

Date of delivery	Contractual	M 12	Actual	31-Aug-09
Status	version. 1		final	
Nature	Report			
Dissemination Level	Public/Confidential			

Authors (Partner)	Fabrice WENDLING, Isabelle MERLET Behnam MOLAEI-ARDEKANI, INSERM			
Responsible Author	Fabrice WENDLING		Email	Fabrice.wendling@univ-rennes1.fr
	Partner	INSERM	Phone	+33 223235605

Abstract (for dissemination)	<p>This report presents the progress accomplished during the first year of the HIVE project in the development of computational models describing the impact of current on neocortical tissue (local level) and on brain neurodynamics (global level). At local level, a neural mass model was developed based on a literature review about the cyto-architecture of the cerebral cortex. Using this model, some necessary conditions were identified to approximate real local field potentials recorded in the rabbit brain under stimulation conditions. At global level, a strategy was defined based on the extension of a model previously published by Inserm. This extension accounts for the main neocortical regions in the human brain and for the connectivity among these regions. The perspective is to solve the EEG forward problem from simulated neocortical sources which activity can be modulated by externally-applied electric fields. Therefore, this model should provide insights into changes occurring in the EEG in response to stimulation (TMS or tDCS).</p>
Keywords	Cerebral cortex, electrical stimulation, computational model, neural mass, LFP, EEG, forward solution

Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev No.	Author	Change
<17-08-09>	001	Fabrice WENDLING	Includes the changes made in response to the HIVE's internal review process.
<20-08-09>	002	Fabrice WENDLING	Includes some last changes to the executive summary

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
TABLE OF CONTENTS	4
1 INTRODUCTION	7
2 COMPUTATIONAL MODELS OF BRAIN ACTIVITY AT LOCAL AND GLOBAL SCALE...	7
2.1 A neural mass model for the cerebral cortex	8
2.1.1 Level of modeling and schematic diagram of the proposed model	8
2.1.2 Literature review about the cellular organization of cerebral cortex.....	9
2.1.2.1 Connections from pyramidal cells (1, 2, 3, 4).....	10
2.1.2.2 Connections onto pyramidal cells (5, 6, 12).....	12
2.1.2.3 Connections among interneurons (7, 8, 9, 10, 11)	14
2.1.3 Formal description of the model	15
2.1.3.1 Model structure and equations	15
2.1.3.2 Time constants of glutamatergic and gabaergic PSPs.....	18
2.1.4 Coupling between neuronal populations and externally-applied electric field	19
2.1.5 Simulation software: main functionalities	21
2.1.5.1 Managing the simulation parameters: the main window and the neuronal population inspector	21
2.1.5.2 Managing the stimulation parameters: the stimulator object	22
2.1.5.3 Displaying the cortical responses: the oscilloscope	23
2.1.6 Preliminary results	23
2.1.6.1 Stimulation characteristics	25
2.2 Brain model and EEG generation	28
2.2.1 Getting a realistic model of the sources.....	28
2.2.2 Representing a realistic coupling between cortical regions.....	29
2.2.2.1 The human connectome	30
2.2.2.2 From the human connectome to the generation of brain dynamics ...	31
2.2.3 Computation of electrical potentials on scalp electrodes (forward problem) 33	
2.2.3.1 Basic principles	33
2.2.3.2 Realistic head model and forward calculations.....	34
3 CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES	35
REFERENCES	36
Appendix A	
Appendix B	

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: The development of neurophysiological models in WP1 was divided into two main tasks.	8
Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the neural mass model for the cerebral cortex.	9
Figure 3: Anatomical diversity of neocortical neurons.	11
Figure 4: Structure of the neural mass model for the cerebral cortex.	16
Figure 5: Structure of a generic neuronal population model representing a cluster of neurons composed of two subsets: main cells (i.e. pyramidal cells) and local interneurons (basket cells for instance).	17
Figure 6: Intracellular recordings performed in hippocampal slices.	19
Figure 7: Coupling model between a subpopulation of neurons in the neural mass model and the electric field.	20
Figure 8: Simulation software: main window	21
Figure 9: Simulation software: user interface.	22
Figure 10: Simulation software: stimulation protocols.	22
Figure 11: Simulation software: “oscilloscope”.	23
Figure 12: Reduced model used for the preliminary study of simulated cortical responses.	24
Figure 13: Real signals recorded by UPO.	24
Figure 14: New experiments conducted by UPO	25
Figure 15: a) Simulation of the stimulation effect in the model and b) Typical simulated response obtained by summing the PSPs at the level of pyramidal cells.	26
Figure 16: The two pyramidal cell-interneuron loops in the model.	26
Figure 17: A preliminary result about the simulation of cortical responses using the neuronal population model.	27
Figure 18: Spatio-temporal source model	29
Figure 19: Extraction of a Whole Brain Structural Connectivity Network.	30
Figure 20: Average Regional Connection Matrix, Network Layout, and Connectivity Backbone.	31
Figure 21: Outlined ROIs on our mesh.	32
Figure 22: From the “human connectome” to realistic brain dynamics.	33
Figure 23: Head model.	34

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Quantitative analysis of synaptic connections from interneurons onto pyramidal cells and from pyramidal cells onto interneurons	10
Table 2: Standard values for the amplitude of average post-synaptic potentials and decay time constants used in the model.....	18

1 INTRODUCTION

The long-term vision of our four-year HIVE project is to investigate and develop proof-of-concept technologies for non-invasive machine-to-brain interaction through brain stimulation (or interaction in a more general sense).

HIVE is a typical example for a project where theory and computation must work hand-in-hand with experiment to bring us a deeper understanding of the brain function. Based on computational modelling of electromagnetic currents and of their impacts on neuronal systems, coupled with experimentation in animals and humans, the project shall explore advanced multi-site transcranial current and magnetic stimulation targeting different applications (sleep, direct communication, motor and cognitive learning, sense synthesis, therapy).

Indeed, we decided to tackle the complexity of neuron-current interactions by taking advantage of the integrative virtue of computational models aimed at describing i) the distribution of the electrical field in the brain and ii) the response of neuronal systems for various configurations of this electrical field.

In the present report, we describe the progress accomplished so far in the development of physiologically-plausible models of neuronal assemblies of the cerebral cortex and of neurodynamics of the whole brain.

This report is the first deliverable submitted by Inserm at month 12. A second deliverable will complement this first edition and will be prepared for month 27.

The content is organized according to two main sections. The first main section (2.1) describes the work performed on model development at local level (a neuronal assembly submitted to the influence of an exogenous electrical field). The second main section (2.2) presents the preliminary results regarding the modeling of brain activity at global level (network of neuronal assemblies coupled according to our current knowledge about the human connectome).

2 COMPUTATIONAL MODELS OF BRAIN ACTIVITY AT LOCAL AND GLOBAL SCALE

The two main objectives of WP1 (Biophysical models) is to provide physical models for current propagation in the brain from multi-site electrode and to provide neurophysiological models describing the effect of applied currents on neocortical tissue and on brain neurodynamics and consequently on local field potentials and global EEG generation.

Regarding neurophysiological models, we divided the work into two main tasks as illustrated in Figure 1. The first task consists in the development of a neural mass model aimed at representing local field potentials (LFPs) generated at the level of single neuronal populations located in the cerebral cortex. This model will be tested against data (real LFPs) recorded in the cortex of the rabbit in a defined protocol of electrical stimulation (see WP2: In vivo exploration). The second task is devoted to the development of a brain model aimed at reproducing global field potentials (EEG signals) as recorded in humans. This model will be tested against data (real EEGs) recorded in human subjects under various conditions (see WP3: stimulating the human brain).

At both levels (local and global), proposed models must account for the effects of applied electrical fields separately computed in the physical models also developed in WP1.

Figure 1: The development of neurophysiological models in WP1 was divided into two main tasks: i) development of a neural mass model aimed at representing local field potentials (LFPs) generated at the level of single neuronal populations located in the cerebral cortex and ii) development of a brain model aimed at reproducing global field potentials (EEG signals) as recorded in humans.

2.1 A local neural mass model for the cerebral cortex

2.1.1 Level of modeling and schematic diagram of the proposed model

In order to simulate signals generated in the cerebral cortex in response to the applied electrical field, we designed a physiologically-plausible computational model. It is noteworthy that the level of modeling we used is that of the neuronal assembly. This means that our model considers the average activity of interconnected subpopulations of principal neurons and interneurons without explicit representation of mechanisms lying at the level of single cells, conversely to detailed models. Although macroscopic, these models rely on neurophysiological data and have two essential features. First, their parameters relate to excitatory and inhibitory processes taking place in the considered neuronal tissue. Second, the temporal dynamics of their output (analogous to a local field activity) can be directly compared to those reflected in real signals recorded with electrodes located in the cerebral cortex. Indeed, it can be assumed that field potentials reflect overall dynamics rising from interconnected populations of principal neurons and interneurons.

The macroscopic modeling approach which we developed requires a description of the different subpopulations of cells present in the cerebral cortex as well as a description of synaptic interactions between these subpopulations. This type of approach was first described theoretically by Wilson and Cowan (Wilson HR, 1973) and first used by Freeman (Freeman, 1978) and Lopes Da Silva (Lopes da Silva et al., 1974; Lopes da Silva et al., 1976) for electrophysiological data interpretation. More recently, this class of models was exploited in various neurophysiological or clinical studies. Jansen et al. (Jansen BH, 1995; Jansen BH, 1993) proposed a lumped-parameter model of the visual cortex to study the generation of evoked potentials (1995). Wendling et al. (Wendling et

al., 2002; Wendling et al., 2000; Wendling et al., 2005) elaborated a model for the hippocampus. Suffczynski et al. (Suffczynski et al., 2004) investigated the mechanisms of transition between normal EEG activity and epileptiform paroxysmal activity using a computational macroscopic model of thalamocortical circuits. Bojak and Liley (Bojak and Liley, 2005) also proposed a model of the same type for cortical activity and simulated realistic EEG signals in response to specific and quantifiable physiological changes related to different anesthetic agents.

Therefore, in order to design the model, we started from neurophysiological data about neuronal organization and connectivity of the cerebral cortex. A schematic diagram of the model is proposed in Figure 2. The main features were obtained from the literature. Note that the numbers that are reported on the connections between the subpopulations are provided to facilitate the reading of the review of the literature that is summarized in the next section.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the neural mass model for the cerebral cortex. This schematic is also inserted in the software that was developed by Inserm for easily adjusting the parameters and running the simulations. Italic numbers on connections between subpopulations are provided to facilitate the reading of the review of the literature (section 2.1.2).

2.1.2 Literature review about the cellular organization of cerebral cortex

Neocortical neurons are arranged in layers (layers I–VI) that connect to either cortical or subcortical regions. As an approximation, a neocortical column of about 0.3 mm in diameter contains roughly 7,500 neurons. Most neocortical neurons (70–80%) are excitatory pyramidal neurons which have relatively stereotyped anatomical, physiological and molecular properties. The remaining 20–30% of neocortical neurons are interneurons, mostly inhibitory, which have diverse morphological, physiological, molecular and synaptic characteristics, as illustrated in Figure 3. A summary of the main synaptic connections between pyramidal cells and interneurons is also provided in Table 1.

Synaptic connections from interneurons onto pyramidal cells					
	LBC→PC	NBC→PC	SBC→PC	BTC→PC	MC→PC
Anatomical properties	<i>n</i> = 4 pairs; 58 synapses	<i>n</i> = 6 pairs; 93 synapses	<i>n</i> = 6 pairs; 123 synapses	<i>n</i> = 7 pairs; 105 synapses	<i>n</i> = 9 pairs; 101 synapses
Number of putative synapses	14.5 ± 1.7	15.8 ± 4.1	20.5 ± 10.5	15.0 ± 7.1	11.2 ± 5.5
Innervated dendritic fraction*	0.61	0.78	0.79	0.65	0.46
Neighbouring synapses within 10 μm ²	31%	43%	29%	16%	30%
Geometric distances (<i>L</i>) [‡]	97.06 ± 41.49	68.28 ± 13.14	78.83 ± 20.61	94.30 ± 19.91	163.230 ± 114.10
Electrotonic distances (<i>X</i>) [§]	0.096 ± 0.053	0.078 ± 0.018	0.063 ± 0.014	0.086 ± 0.020	0.141 ± 0.105
Innervating PAC fraction [¶]	0.50	0.83	0.82	0.56	0.70
Percentage of synapses sharing same axonal segments in pairs	53% (4 pairs)	25% (6 pairs)	20% (6 pairs)	31% (7 pairs)	43% (9 pairs)
Percentage of synapses sharing same axonal segments in triples	29% (1 triple)	–	9% (4 triples)	15% (4 triples)	13% (2 triples)
Percentage of synapses sharing same axonal segments in quadruples	–	–	0% (1 quadruple)	0% (1 quadruple)	–

Synaptic connections from pyramidal cells onto interneurons					
	PC→LBC	PC→NBC	PC→SBC	PC→BTC	PC→MC
Anatomical properties	<i>n</i> = 13 pairs; 78 synapses	<i>n</i> = 5 pairs; 17 synapses	No pair recorded	<i>n</i> = 10 pairs; 63 synapses	<i>n</i> = 13 pairs; 98 synapses
Number of putative synapses	7.1 ± 3.1	3.4 ± 1.5	–	7.0 ± 4.3	8.2 ± 5.0
Innervated dendritic fraction*	0.19	0.26	–	0.44	0.42
Neighbouring synapses within 10 μm ²	53%	41%	–	60%	35%
Geometric distances (<i>L</i>) [‡]	93.33 ± 53.93	54.58 ± 30.86	–	203.30 ± 202.90	199.35 ± 87.73
Electrotonic distances (<i>X</i>) [§]	0.083 ± 0.030	0.041 ± 0.027	–	0.205 ± 0.247	0.209 ± 0.097
Percentage of synapses sharing same dendritic segments in pairs	53% (13 pairs)	55% (5 pairs)	–	69% (10 pairs)	37% (13 pairs)
Percentage of synapses sharing same dendritic segments in triples	18% (7 triples)	0% (1 triple)	–	58% (5 triples)	28% (5 triples)
Percentage of synapses sharing same dendritic segments in quadruples	0% (2 quadruples)	–	–	64% (1 quadruple)	0% (1 quadruple)
Innervating PAC fraction [¶]	–	–	–	–	–
Percentage of synapses sharing same axonal segments in pairs	67%	76%	–	75%	55%
Percentage of synapses sharing same axonal segments in triples	–	–	–	–	–
Percentage of synapses sharing same axonal segments in quadruples	–	–	–	–	–

Quantitative analysis of synaptic connections. The analysis was carried out on the basis of three-dimensional computer-reconstructed pairs, triples and quadruples of synaptic connections. *The fraction of dendritic trees of a postsynaptic cell receiving contacts from a presynaptic cell. †The percentage of synapses located less than 10 μm from each other on the structures of a postsynaptic cell. ‡The distance from a putative synapse to the soma. §Computed according to: $X = L/\lambda$ and $\lambda = \sqrt{(R_m r/2R_i)}$, where *L* = geometric length, *r* = mean dendritic radius, *R_i* = internal resistivity (155 Ω cm), and *R_m* = membrane resistance (70,000 Ω cm²). ¶The fraction of the primary axonal collaterals (PAC; collaterals branched from the main axon stem) used to innervate a postsynaptic cell. BTC, binuffed cell; LBC, large basket cell; MC, Martinotti cell; NBC, nest basket cell; PC, pyramidal cell; SBC, small basket cell.

Table 1: Quantitative analysis of synaptic connections from interneurons onto pyramidal cells and from pyramidal cells onto interneurons. Adapted from (Thomson et al., 1996). For this report, permission has not been requested

2.1.2.1 Connections from pyramidal cells (1, 2, 3, 4)

a) Pyramid–Pyramid connections (1)

Pyramidal cells are the largest broad class of neurons in cortex (60–90% depending on region and layer). They permit most of the cortico-cortical and extra-cortical projections, as well as a substantial proportion of the local excitatory connections within neocortical circuits (DeFelipe and Fariñas, 1992). Neocortical pyramidal cells are extensively interconnected (Somogyi et al., 1998). The majority of the connections made by pyramidal axons are with spiny postsynaptic dendrites, indicating that many of their targets are other pyramidal cells (Kisvárdy *et al.*, 1986; Elhanany and White, 1990; White and Czeiger, 1991; Kisvárdy and Eysel, 1992; Czeiger and White, 1993; Keller, 1993; Keller and Asanuma, 1993; Johnson and Burkhalter, 1996). Numerically, therefore, connections between pyramidal cells, including close neighbours, cells in different layers and cells in different regions, are a dominant feature of the cortical circuit (Thomson and Deuchars, 1997).

Figure 3: Anatomical diversity of neocortical neurons. Scheme summarizing the main anatomical properties of neocortical inhibitory interneurons. Each neuron type has a different coloured soma; dendrites, red; axons, blue lines; axonal boutons, blue dots. Spines are omitted for clarity. Neurons are orientated with the pia facing upwards and white matter downwards. Some interneurons have a prominent, vertical dendrite directed towards the white matter. Inhibitory interneurons are mainly distinguished by the structure of their axonal arbour and typically innervate selective domains ((peri-) somatic, dendritic or axonal) of their target cells. From (Markram et al., 2004). For this report, permission has not been requested.

Studies about the synaptic targets of local pyramidal collaterals have shown that they establish synapses mostly with dendritic spines (Somogyi et al., 1998). The proportion of spines as postsynaptic targets varies from about 85% between layer 2/3 pyramidal cells to about 30% in the layer 6 to layer 4 (Somogyi et al., 1998). Similar to the long range cortico-cortical connections, the local pyramidal interconnections are mediated by both NMDA and AMPA type glutamate receptors (Thomson and Deuchars, 1997).

Cortical neurons receive the great majority of their synaptic inputs from neurons within the local network (i.e. < 1 mm distant) (Binzegger et al., 2004). Consequently, the activity of the local network will have a dominating, but not exclusive, influence on the membrane potential of nearby cells (Haider and McCormick, 2009).

b) Pyramid-to-interneurons connections (2,3,4)

To date, there is no universally accepted taxonomy of cortical interneurons. Classification schemes vary from a dozen of relatively well-defined classes to a single

class considering interneurons with virtually unlimited heterogeneity (Buzsaki et al., 2004). GABAergic interneurons represent a minor fraction of the total neuron number in the neocortex (around 20%) but are crucial for normal brain function (Wang et al., 1999). Only 10–15% of synapses are inhibitory, mainly originating from neighboring GABAergic interneurons (Silberberg, 2008).

Principal neuron–interneuron synapses, like the majority of glutamatergic synapses, rely mainly on AMPA receptors. However, their functional properties are highly specialized. First, unitary excitatory postsynaptic potentials (EPSPs) and excitatory postsynaptic currents (EPSCs) have a rapid time course (Bartos et al., 2007).

Glutamatergic synapses on interneurons are stronger than those on principal neurons. For instance, in the hippocampal CA3 region, a unitary synaptic event can be sufficient to drive the postsynaptic interneuron to firing threshold. Moreover, there is a ~fourfold higher density of AMPA R on interneuron than at neighbouring synapses on principal neurons (Bartos et al., 2007).

c) Pyramidal cells to basket / chandelier cells (2)

About 50% of all inhibitory interneurons are basket cells. It is now commonly admitted that basket cells mostly target the somata and proximal dendrites of pyramidal neurons and interneurons. This propriety puts them in a unique position to adjust the gain of the integrated synaptic response (Markram et al., 2004). Several lines of evidence indicate that fast-spiking basket cells play an essential role in the generation of gamma oscillations both *in vivo* and *in vitro*. Recent reports (Bartos et al., 2007) showed that inhibitory synapses between basket cells could synchronize action potential activity within the basket cell network. Conversely inhibitory synapses between basket cells and principal neurons could distribute this synchronized activity to the principal neuron population. In addition, many studies have emphasized the role of basket cells in the generation of fast oscillations observed in local field potentials. In particular, gamma activity is associated with alternating current sources and sinks in the perisomatic region. This finding is consistent with the involvement of basket cells, which precisely innervate this subcellular domain (Bartos et al., 2007).

d) Pyramidal cells to double bouquet and bitufted cells in the neocortex (3)

Double bouquet cells (DBC) are neocortical GABAergic interneurons characterized by the vertical bundling of its axonal direction. Bitufted cells are only found in layers II–V. They have an elongated soma that generally lies perpendicular to the pia, with most of the dendritic trees emerging from the top and bottom of the soma. Several studies (Deuchars and Thomson, 1995; Somogyi et al., 1998) have shown that double bouquet and bitufted cells in the neocortex are activated at least in part in recurrent activation (principal neurons excite this population that in turn inhibits the activity of the first).

2.1.2.2 Connections onto pyramidal cells (5, 6, 12)

GABAergic synapses cover almost the entire membrane surface of pyramidal neurons, from the tips of their thinnest dendritic shafts to the axon initial segments (Freund and Katona, 2007).

a) Basket cells to pyramidal cells (5)

In a study by Pearce, it has been shown that monosynaptic GABA_A fast-mediated IPSCs can be recorded in pyramidal neurons (Pearce, 1993). GABA_A fast current enters at or near the cell body, decays rapidly (3-8 ms), and rapidly curtails the excitatory response. GABA_{A,fast} is a rapidly activated, rapidly decaying IPSC mediated by somatic and proximal dendritic synapses, likely arising from basket and chandelier cells, as well as other interneurons projecting to these regions (Freund and Buzsaki, 1996). Its location and time course allow this inhibitory current to control the timing and occurrence of pyramidal cell output in response to a given excitatory input (Banks et al., 2000; Miles et al., 1996). The fast spiking basket cell (FSBC)-evoked unitary GABA_A IPSCs (FSBC-IPSCA) that are thought to represent GABA_{A,fast} events (Banks et al., 2000; Jonas et al., 2004) (Overstreet et al., 2000). Interestingly the pharmacology of these FSBC-PC synapses is that they contain GABA_A receptors, which are typically associated with “fast” GABA_A receptor-mediated neurotransmission in the cortex (Bacci et al., 2003).

b) Chandelier cells to pyramidal cells (5)

The axon initial segments receive synaptic inputs selectively from another specialized GABAergic interneuron type, the axo-axonic or chandelier cells (Somogyi, 1977). This cell type has recently received considerable attention as a result of a discovery that GABAergic inputs targeting the axon initial segment have a depolarized reversal potential compared to those innervating the somatic domain due to higher intracellular chloride concentrations. Therefore, axo-axonic cells may discharge rather than inhibit their postsynaptic pyramidal cells (Szabadics et al., 2006). However this point remain controversial, because a recent noninvasive approach showed that hippocampal interneurons hyperpolarized pyramidal cells irrespective of the location of their synapses along the somato dendritic axis (Glickfeld et al., 2009).

c) Double bouquet cells to pyramidal cells (12)

Double bouquet cells (DBC) mainly innervate dendrites (spines and shafts) of pyramidal cells and are therefore dendritic-targeting cells. DBCs occur in layers II–V, although they seem to be preferentially located in the supragranular layers (Markram et al., 2004).

d) Neuroglialform cells to pyramidal cells (6)

Neuroglialform cells (NGFCs) are multipolar cells with dendrites that branch close to the cell body and have a dense axonal plexus and they are characterized by a late-spiking firing pattern. NGFCs generate slow GABA_A postsynaptic responses on pyramidal cells in the neocortex, as demonstrated in (Szabadics et al., 2007). Other studies have also shown GABAB-mediated inhibition in postsynaptic pyramidal cells after a single action potential in NGFCs in the neocortex (Tamas et al., 2003). GABA_B receptors are often located perisynaptically, and their activation after NGFC activation suggests spillover from the synapse after a single action potential (Krook-Magnuson and Huntsman, 2007).

2.1.2.3 *Connections among interneurons (7, 8, 9, 10, 11)*

Synapses between basket cells (BCs) are more numerous and located closer to the soma than synapses mediating BC-to-DBC (double bouquet cells) or DBC-to-BC interactions (Somogyi et al., 1998). First, it is rare to record connections between interneurons, indicating that they are sparsely connected. Second, connections between interneurons are also mediated by multiple synapses (an average of around ten). Third, interneurons can target specific domains of other interneurons. Last, inhibitory synapses onto interneurons are highly distributed on the dendrites, as for pyramidal neurons.

Basket cells innervate neighbouring basket cells, dendritic-targeting cells and DBCs. These synapses are located somatically and peri-somatically, but whereas both dendritic-targeting cells and DBCs receive only a few synapses, postsynaptic basket cells receive more. Such differences have been interpreted to indicate both selectivity and preference in inhibitory neocortical microcircuits. The large numbers of synapses between basket cells might underlie extensive basket-cell networks, which have been implicated in long-range lateral disinhibition. Activity in such networks might also be coordinated by electrical synapses.

a) Basket cells to basket cells (7)

Connections from basket to basket cells have been identified in many studies. The time course of the GABA-mediated inhibitory postsynaptic currents (IPSCs) in neocortical fast-spiking interneurons (BC-BC) was observed to be markedly faster than the kinetics of IPSCs in principal neurons of the same circuit (Bartos et al., 2002; Galarreta and Hestrin, 2002). Paired recording experiments in acute slices *in vitro* have shown that basket cells are highly interconnected in the neocortex (Bartos et al., 2007). For example, the probability of finding a chemical synaptic coupling between two closely spaced fast-spiking, parvalbumin-expressing basket cells in the dentate gyrus is ~50%. An independent estimate of connectivity was obtained by neuroanatomical approaches, indicating that each parvalbumin-positive basket cell is connected to at least 60 other basket cells (Bartos et al., 2007).

Furthermore, paired recording analysis showed that synapses between basket cells have specialized functional properties. First, evoked GABA_A-receptor-mediated IPSCs in these cells show surprisingly rapid kinetics. After a delay, caused by axonal action potential propagation (conduction delay) and transmitter release (synaptic delay), IPSCs rise almost instantaneously and decay with a time constant of ~2-3 ms at near-physiological temperature. Fast inhibition is target-cell specific. IPSCs at basket cell–basket cell synapses are about twice as fast as IPSCs at basket cell–principal neuron synapses (Bartos et al., 2007).

b) Neurogliaform cells to basket cells (10)

Neurogliaform cells establish electrical synapses not only with each other but also with other interneuron types in the neocortex (Price et al., 2005; Simon et al., 2005; Zsiros and Maccaferri, 2005). Neurogliaform cells link multiple networks of interneurons. They were suggested to play a key role in generating and shaping synchronized activity of neuronal circuits (Simon et al., 2005; Zsiros and Maccaferri, 2005). Most interneurons trigger fast inhibitory postsynaptic potentials (IPSPs) in their postsynaptic target cells mediated by GABA_A receptors (Buhl et al., 1994; Gupta et al., 2000; Tamas

et al., 2003). By contrast, neurogliaform cells are the only known type of interneuron capable of eliciting slow, long-lasting IPSPs through a combined activation of GABA_A and GABA_B receptors (Tamas et al., 2003). Till now, this effect of neurogliaform cells has been demonstrated only on postsynaptic pyramidal cells (Tamas et al., 2003).

c) Basket cells to Neuroglial form cells (11)

In our literature review, we did not find reports about possible connections from basket cells to neuroglial form cells.

d) Neuroglia form cells to neuroglia form cells (9)

This type of connection is reported in Olah et al., 2007. The rise times and half-width of IPSPs in these connections were 16.5 ± 8.5 and 184.9 ± 96.5 ms, respectively. When comparing IPSPs arriving to postsynaptic pyramidal cells (not shown) and interneurons in the human sample, authors could not detect significant differences in 10–90% rise times and half-widths (20.1 ± 9.8 ms and 12.7 ± 6.8 ; 230.4 ± 64.6 ms and 148.6 ± 108.4 , respectively). For comparison, 10–90% rise times and half-width of IPSPs evoked by neurogliaform cells in rat pyramidal cells were 23.4 ± 9.8 ms and 183.9 ± 82.5 (Tamas et al., 2003). Slow IPSPs were combined with homologous and heterologous electrical coupling between neurogliaform cells and several human interneuron types. In the rat, single action potentials in neurogliaform cells elicited GABA_B receptor-mediated component in responses of neurogliaform, regular spiking, and fast spiking interneurons following the GABA_A receptor-mediated component in postsynaptic responses (Olah et al., 2007). Neurogliaform cells are not only coupled with other neurogliaform cells (Juhász et al., 2009) but also with FS-PV and putative adapting SOM neurons (Simon et al., 2005). Neuroglial-like cell are highly electrically coupled in the neocortex (Juhász et al., 2009).

2.1.3 Formal description of the model

2.1.3.1 Model structure and equations

The structure of the computational model we developed is based on the literature review summarized in the previous section. In this macroscopic class of models, a population of cells is considered. This population is composed by different subpopulations of cells (typically principal cells and interneurons) which interact via synaptic connections. Our model accounts for the main types of cells present in the cerebral cortex:

- pyramidal cells,
- axon-, soma- and proximal dendrite-targeting cells: basket cells and chandelier cells (type 1 interneurons mediating GABA_A, fast currents),
- dendrite-targeting cells: bitufted, bipolar and double bouquet cells (type 2 interneurons mediating GABA_A, fast currents),
- dendrite-targeting cells: neurogliaform cells (type 3 interneurons mediating GABA_A, slow and GABA_B currents),

and for the main synaptic interactions (glutamatergic and gabaergic) described in the previous section. Therefore, the contribution of stellate cells and Martinotti cells to the

network activity is neglected in the model. This assumption is reasonable in regard with the lesser representation of these cells in the neocortex. The model structure is summarized in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Structure of the neural mass model for the cerebral cortex. Thin lines (among interneurons) indicate that the connections are less numerous

As shown in the simple example in Figure 5, at each subpopulation, a pulse-to-wave function transforms the average presynaptic pulse density of afferent action potentials (input) into an average postsynaptic membrane potential (output) whereas a wave-to-pulse function relates the average postsynaptic potential to an average pulse density of potentials fired by the neurons. The pulse-to-wave function is represented by a 2nd order linear transfer function impulse response $h(t) = W.t.w.e^{-wt}$ (eq. 1) where W is the amplitude of the average receptor-mediated postsynaptic potential (denoted as \overline{EPSP} in the excitatory case and as \overline{IPSP} in the inhibitory case) and where w represents the decay time constant of this postsynaptic potential. The wave-to-pulse function is modeled by a static nonlinear function of sigmoid shape $S(v) = 2e0 / [1 + e^{r(v0-v)}]$ to represent saturation and threshold effects taking place at the soma.

Besides synaptic transmission, interactions between neuronal subsets are also characterized in the model by connectivity constants (CP_{Ix} , CP_P , CIx_{Ix} , CIx_P where x is 1, 2 or 3) which account for the average number of synaptic contacts or “degree of connection”.

The non specific influence from neighboring or distant populations is represented by a Gaussian input noise corresponding to an excitatory input $p(t)$ that globally describes the average density of afferent action potentials.

One model output corresponds to the postsynaptic activity of principal neurons (summed postsynaptic potentials) and can be interpreted as a field potential. Others possible model outputs correspond to the postsynaptic activity of subpopulations, allowing to assess the participation of each cellular type in the observed field activity.

Finally, model equations are derived from functions $h(t)$ (eq. 1) which introduce a pair of first order ordinary differential equations of the form : $z'_1(t) = z_2(t)$ and $z'_2(t) = Ww x(t) - 2w z_2(t) - w^2 z_1(t)$ where $x(t)$ and $z(t)$ are the respective input (afferent pulse density) and output (average postsynaptic membrane potential) signals. For a given model, the set of first order nonlinear ordinary differential equations obtained for all synaptic interactions present in the model is numerically solved using standard integration algorithms (fixed step Euler method) to simulate signals.

Figure 5: a) Structure of a generic neuronal population model representing a cluster of neurons composed of two subsets: main cells (i.e. pyramidal cells) and local interneurons (basket cells for instance). Pyramidal cells receive excitatory input from other pyramidal cells (collateral excitation) or inhibitory input from interneurons. These latter cells receive excitatory input only from pyramidal cells. b) Each subset is characterized by two functions, respectively named as the “pulse-to-wave function” and the “wave-to-pulse function”. The former changes presynaptic information (average density of afferent action potentials) into postsynaptic information (average excitatory or inhibitory postsynaptic membrane potential, respectively EPSP or IPSP). The latter relates the average level of membrane potential of the neurons to an average pulse density of potentials fired by these neurons. c) Impulse response of the “pulse-to-wave function” approximating actual average excitatory (dotted line) or inhibitory (solid line) postsynaptic potentials. d) Shape of the “wave-to-pulse” function. Nonlinear sigmoid shape accounts for the integrating action that takes place at the soma (threshold and saturation effects). From (Wendling and Chauvel, 2008). For this report, permission has not been requested.

Following these above general principles and according to the detailed description reported in the previous section, we established a model for the cerebral cortex. The model consists in four interconnected modules corresponding respectively to the subpopulations of cells (pyramidal, type 1, type 2, type 3 interneurons).

In addition, for each type of synaptic interaction, equation 1 turns into

$$h_1(t) = \overline{EPSP} \cdot \tau_1 \cdot t \cdot e^{-\tau_1 \cdot t} \text{ for excitatory } \overline{PSP} \text{ s (Glu)}$$

$$h_2(t) = \overline{IPSP}_{GABA_{a,s}} \cdot \tau_2 \cdot t \cdot e^{-\tau_2 \cdot t} \text{ for slow inhibitory GABA}_a \text{ } \overline{PSP} \text{ s (GABA}_{a,\text{slow}})$$

$$h_3(t) = \overline{IPSP}_{GABA_{a,f}} \cdot \tau_3 \cdot t \cdot e^{-\tau_3 \cdot t} \text{ for fast inhibitory GABA}_a \text{ } \overline{PSP} \text{ s (GABA}_{a,\text{fast}})$$

$$h_4(t) = \overline{IPSP}_{GABA_b} \cdot \tau_4 \cdot t \cdot e^{-\tau_4 \cdot t} \text{ for inhibitory GABA}_b \text{ } \overline{PSP} \text{ s (GABA}_b)$$

with $t \geq 0$ and where \overline{EPSP} denotes the amplitude of the average excitatory glutamate-mediated postsynaptic potential, \overline{IPSP}_i stands for the amplitude of the average inhibitory postsynaptic potential mediated by receptors of type i and where $1/\tau_j$ represents the corresponding decay time constant, as described in the next section.

2.1.3.2 Time constants of glutamatergic and gabaergic PSPs

Regarding glutamatergic currents, Kidd and Isaac showed that the EPSC decays were best fitted by the sum of two exponentials ($\tau_{\text{fast}} = 5.9 \pm 0.5$ ms, $\tau_{\text{slow}} = 169.2 \pm 16.7$ ms) (Kidd and Isaac, 1999). The fast component of the EPSC was mediated by AMPA receptors. According to this value, we will adjust the value of $1/\tau_1$ at about 6 ms (4.5 – 7.5).

For gabaergic currents, monosynaptic GABA_a fast-mediated IPSCs were recorded in pyramidal neurons (Pearce 1993). Decay times were estimated to vary in the range of 3-8 ms. For GABA_{a,slow} synapses, falling time constants of 50 \pm 20 ms are commonly used (White et al., 2000). Finally, for GABA_b-mediated IPSCs, based on current recordings performed under paired-pulse technique, the study reported in (Deisz, 1999) showed time constants ranging approximately from 200 to 400 ms in neocortical neurons of the rat in vitro. Therefore, the value of $1/\tau_4$ can adjusted in this range of values. Table 2 provides a summary of time constants to be used in the model.

	Average amplitude (mV)	Decay time (ms)
Excitatory PSP (Glutamate)	$\overline{EPSP} = 3 - 8$	$1/\tau_1 = 4.5 - 7.5$
Inhibitory PSP (GABA _{a,slow})	$\overline{IPSP}_{GABA_{a,s}} = 1 - 40$	$1/\tau_2 = 30 - 70$
Inhibitory PSP (GABA _{a,fast})	$\overline{IPSP}_{GABA_{a,f}} = 1 - 40$	$1/\tau_3 = 3 - 8$
Inhibitory PSP (GABA _b)	$\overline{IPSP}_{GABA_b} = 1 - 5$	$1/\tau_4 = 200 - 400$

Table 2: Standard values for the amplitude of average post-synaptic potentials and decay time constants used in the model

2.1.4 Coupling between neuronal populations and an externally-applied electric field

In order to account for the influence of the electric field resulting from the externally-applied stimulation in our neuronal mass model, we have to introduce a model for the coupling between the neuronal population and the stimulation effects.

From the literature review we performed in WP1 (see D1.1 REVIEW OF STATE-OF-THE-ART IN CURRENTS DISTRIBUTION AND EFFECTS), it can be assumed that, within a certain range of intensity, the applied electric field linearly modifies the average membrane potential at the level of the different sub-populations. An example obtained from experimental data obtained in vitro is provided in Figure 6. From intracellular recordings (effects on single pyramidal cells of CA1), authors (Bikson et al., 2004) confirmed that application of exogenous uniform electric fields parallel to the soma–dendritic axis results in changes in transmembrane potential (all recorded neurons): positive (respectively negative) fields resulted in somatic hyperpolarization (respectively depolarization).

Figure 6: Intracellular recordings performed in hippocampal slices in vitro (A) during application of an external electric field influence. A) The cell membrane polarization and B) action potential threshold vary (almost) linearly with the strength of the applied electric field. Adapted from (Bikson et al., 2004). For this report, permission has not been requested.

For formal description of this model of coupling (referred to as the “Lambda.E model”) readers may also refer to the STARLAB Technical Note TN00172 entitled “Single-neuron and lumped model stimulation coupling” by G. Ruffini (March 26, 2009).

This technical note is provided in appendix A.

In this section, we summarize the main aspects of this model. As shown in many studies reported in D1.1, neurons are sensitive to the externally-applied electric field component that is oriented along their main axis. As illustrated in figure 7-a, this component (blue) can be obtained by computing the scalar product between the field (red) and a unit vector along the somato-dendritic axis y of the cells. This component \vec{E}_y (weighted by a scalar lambda determined from experimental data) is then added to the average membrane potential of the different subpopulations of neurons (pyramidal cells and interneurons) represented in the neuronal mass model. When positive (respectively negative), it will have a depolarizing (respectively polarizing) effect.

In addition, it must be added that the computation of the electric-field component \vec{E}_y will be provided by the physical models for current propagation developed by FFCUL in WP1 (see D1.2 v1).

Finally, it is well-established that the electric field primarily affects the main cells. However, several studies also mention its potential influence on interneurons, although this effect has not been fully characterized due to the experimental difficulties of recording from interneurons. Regarding this issue, the model might be used to investigate this relative effect of the field onto pyramidal cells on the one hand and onto interneurons on the other hand, as mentioned in the perspectives (section 3).

Our intent is to validate the model based on in vivo data recorded in the cerebral cortex of the rabbit by UPO (D3.2 v1). Some preliminary results are described in section 2.1.6 based on preliminary data shown by UPO. Some model predictions like the relative effect of the field on the different subpopulations of neurons in the cortex could also be tested experimentally (see section 3 Perspectives).

Figure 7: Coupling model between a subpopulation of neurons in the neural mass model and the electric field resulting from the externally-applied stimulation. a) Schematic diagram showing a given subpopulation of cells, its input and output and the projection of the field vector on the main axis of the cells (blue color) b) According to this model of interaction, the variation of the average membrane potential of a given subpopulation is proportional to the intensity of the component of the electric field oriented along the main axis of the cells.

2.1.5 Simulation software: main functionalities

For the purpose of HIVE, the model was implemented using an object-oriented language (objective C) which allows us to manipulate populations of neurons as objects that can be interconnected in order to form networks of populations of neurons (see section 2.2). In addition, we also developed a dedicated software to facilitate the investigation of the model. This software allows for easy i) modification of parameters in each object, ii) management of the stimulation parameters and iii) display of the model output (a local field potential generated spontaneously or in response to the stimulation).

A brief description of these software capabilities is provided hereafter.

2.1.5.1 *Managing the simulation parameters: the main window and the neuronal population inspector*

The main window (Figure 8) of the simulation software allows the user to adjust the main simulation parameters: number of instantiated populations of neurons (see next paragraph), connectivity and associated delay values, simulation duration, sampling frequency. It also offers some functionalities for creation/deletion of populations, copy/paste of parameters from a population to another and specification of the population that is inspected using the “oscilloscope” object (see section 2.1.5.3).

Figure 8: Simulation software. The main window provides access to the principal objects and parameters used in the simulation

From the main window, all population objects instantiated for the simulation purpose can be inspected, as illustrated in Figure 9. The graphical interface provides access to the “internal” parameters of each population: amplitude and decay time of EPSPs and IPSPs, connection strengths within and between subpopulations and input noise parameters (mean and variance).

Figure 9: Simulation software. A user-friendly interface was developed in order to adjust the parameters associated with the population of neurons instantiated for the simulation purpose.

2.1.5.2 Managing the stimulation parameters: the stimulator object

The simulation software allows for stimulating the neuronal populations. The coupling between the model and the externally-applied field is described in section 2.1.4. At present, this object allows for application of a square, sinusoidal or piecewise linear stimulation function. Stimulation parameters include amplitude, duration and period (in the case of repetitive stimuli). This object can still be improved. In particular, future development will include the possibility to weight the field amplitude depending on the type of subpopulation being stimulated. This point is discussed in section 3.

Figure 10: Simulation software. Various types of stimulation protocols can be defined using the “stimulation manager”.

2.1.5.3 Displaying the cortical responses: the oscilloscope

We also developed a special object for displaying the results of the simulations. This object is called “oscilloscope” in reference to the equipment that is traditionally used in electrophysiology in order to display signals recorded from neurons. Besides displaying the local field activity (summated PSPs at the level of pyramidal cells), the oscilloscope offers a lot of capabilities: representation of the activity (firing rate and membrane potential) of individual subpopulations, computation of the power spectra, zooming scaling, copy/paste of curves, etc. An example is illustrated in Figure 11 which shows the signals generated by the model in response to a square stimulus (1 mV, 1 ms) arising at time $t = 1$ sec.

Figure 11: Simulation software. A special object called “oscilloscope” was designed to display the various signals generated by the model: local field potential (spontaneous or induced by stimulation), firing rate and average membrane potentials at the level of pyramidal cells and interneurons.

2.1.6 Preliminary results

In this section we report the results obtained from the investigation of the model. In order to limit the complexity, we explored a reduced version of the model, i.e. we removed the type 2 interneurons. This procedure can be justified as follows. As explained in section 2.1.3, neural mass models are mainly intended to represent synaptic interactions as synaptic currents are the main contributors to local field potentials. In addition, as observed in Figure 4, the loop involving this subpopulation is identical to that involving the type 1 interneurons. Theoretically, it can be shown that merging the two subpopulations (type 1 and type 2) or keeping only one subpopulation (type 1) is structurally equivalent. Therefore, we retained this second option as a reasonable step to begin with. The reduced model is shown in Figure 12.

In this first investigation, our objective was to try to reproduce the time-course of actual cortical responses recorded by UPO in the rabbit and shown at the Virtual Meeting VM1 (Dec 2008). The goal of this meeting was to provide a first literature review and preliminary results about neurophysiological models of brain activity under stimulation condition. The key elements presented by Inserm during VM1 are reported in appendix B.

Figure 12: Reduced model used for the preliminary study of simulated cortical responses

An example is provided in Figure 13. In this example, four intra-cerebral electrodes E1-E4 are inserted in the thickness of the cerebral cortex and record local field potentials. Eight stimulating electrodes are positioned along a circle around the recording electrodes. Any pair of opposite electrodes can be used for stimulation (one anode and one cathode) which consisted here as a square stimulus (duration 50 μ s, amplitude 1mA). Responses recorded on electrodes E1-E4 nearly correspond to damped oscillations with positive and negative waves at various latencies.

Figure 13: Real signals recorded by UPO. Cerebral cortex of the rabbit. Figure shown UPO at the Virtual Meeting (Dec. 2008).

One should also mention that UPO will also perform recordings of field potentials at different intracortical sites with different locations of electrodes, using different amplitude delay, and frequency of pulses, as illustrated in Figure 14.

These new recordings will be used in the development of the physical model (elaborated) by FFCUL for current propagation in the cortex and for estimation of the electric field distribution, in space. Weighted by a constant λ , this estimation of the electric field distribution will then be used as the stimulation function in the neuronal population model (see section 2.1.4).

Figure 14: New experiments conducted by UPO. In this case two recorded electrodes will be implanted in the cortex. These data will be used in the development of the physical model for current propagation by FFCUL. Adapted from Deliverable D2.1: IN-VIVO EXPERIMENTAL PLANS, JM Delgado García et al., UPO - Release date: May 14, 2009

2.1.6.1 Stimulation characteristics

In the simulation, we used rectangular pulses of 1 mV amplitude and 1 ms duration.

It is very important to underline that the aforementioned amplitude value is meaningless, at present. Indeed, a calibration is still needed to bridge between this stimulation value and the effective value of the electric field induced, inside the cortical layer, by the external stimulation. This calibration will be performed using the model developed by FFCUL aimed at estimating the electric field distribution based on an ellipsoidal representation of the rabbit head volume. Then, this value will be weighted by a constant ' λ ' to obtain the amount of variation of the mean membrane potential (see section 2.1.4).

At this stage, we also assumed that the stimulation affects only the subpopulation of pyramidal cells (future works will include simulation studies in which both pyramidal and interneurons populations will be affected with different weight). A typical response is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: a) Simulation of the stimulation effect in the model and b) Typical simulated response obtained by summing the PSPs at the level of pyramidal cells.

a) Distinct influence of the two pyramidal cells-interneurons loops

In order to characterize the relationship between the whole field response and the relative contribution of the different modules in the model, we proceeded to a study of the different loops, taken separately as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: The two pyramidal cell-interneuron loops in the model. Left: inhibition is mediated by fast GABAergic currents. Right: inhibition is mediated by slower GABAergic currents. Decay times are provided in Table 2.

In the first case (Figure 16, left), four types of responses to external stimulation (according to feedback gains):

- Bi-exponential (monophasic)
- Modulated Bi-exponential (biphasic)
- Bi-exponential + Modulated Bi-exponential
- Purely oscillating

In the second case (Figure 16, right), the same four types of responses to external stimulation could be obtained with, however, a lower oscillating frequency. In both cases, we were not able to reproduce the positive and negative waves that occur in actual responses at defined latencies. Therefore, we concluded that none of the 2 above loops could, by itself, lead to the generation of “realistic” responses.

b) Conjoint influence of the two pyramidal cell-interneuron loops

It could be inferred from the tests described above that the model must include PYR cells, type 1 and type 3 interneurons in order to more accurately reproduce the cortical responses observed in the rabbit. Further tests led us to conclude that the pyramidal cell

subpopulation should be connected at least two different types of interneurons and that these interneurons should provide input to pyramidal cells at the level of fast GABAergic synapses (I1) and slow GABAergic synapses (I3). Consequently we then investigated the model including the three subpopulations. In particular, we studied the influence of the excitatory/inhibitory connection strengths.

As a preliminary result, we managed to approximate actual responses shown in Figure 17-b with the model shown in Figure 17-a. This study has to be confirmed based on accurate processing of data acquired in further experiments made by UPO (see Figure 14).

a)

b)

Figure 17: A preliminary result about the simulation of cortical responses using the neuronal population model. a) model configuration for which the actual cortical response was best approximated. b) visual comparison between real (left) and simulated (right) signals. The red vertical bar denotes the stimulation time in the computational model. The stimulation artefact is not represented here.

2.2 A global brain model for EEG generation

In this section we describe the second part of the accomplished work. Here, the objective is to develop a brain model that can reproduce global field potentials (EEG signals) as recorded in human subjects. This global model will help us to interpret EEG data recorded under “normal” and “stimulation” conditions. It will make use of the neuronal population model presented in the previous section and aimed at describing the local cortical activity.

2.2.1 Getting a realistic model of the sources

Our model is an extended version of a previous model (Cosandier-Rimele et al., 2007; Cosandier-Rimele et al., 2008) developed in the context of scalp EEG interpretation in epileptic patients. It combines 1) a distributed dipole source model that describes the spatial features of the sources and 2) the model of coupled neuronal populations (as described in section 2.1). Model number 2 simulates the time-courses associated to the dipole sources and we will refer to it as the “temporal dynamics” in the following.

In this model, it is assumed that the neocortex is organized as a network of neuronal populations. The electrical activity of each population is represented by a current dipole (characterized by its location, orientation and intensity). In order to constrain the dipole locations and orientations, a realistic mesh of the cortical surface (grey matter/white matter interface) is built from the segmentation of a T1-weighted 3D-MRI, using the BrainVisa software (SHFJ, Orsay, France). This mesh is made of 210054 elementary triangles (mean surface 1 mm²) that precisely describe the circumvolutions of the cortical surface (see Figure 18A).

This mesh is a common framework for FFCUL and INSERM (WP1, activity A1.2. Page 25 of the HIVE project Annex 1). FFCUL will provide the distribution, in space and in time, of the electric field “transcranially” induced by the stimulation. INSERM will incorporate these results in the calculation of scalp EEG signals given that the electric field modifies the activity of neuronal population (see section 2.1.4). To start with, we built a cortical surface mesh from the same MRI data (MRI volume “colin27”, see Figure 18) as those used by FFCUL for the estimation of field distribution induced by the stimulation.

This mesh defines our source space. One dipole is located at the barycenter of each triangle and oriented normally to its surface (Figure 18B). At each 3D location x , the dipole intensity $I(x,t)$, function of space and time, is written as the product of two terms:

$$I(x,t) = q(x) * \alpha(t)$$

where $q(x)$ denotes the dipole moment (function of space) and $\alpha(t)$ is a weighting coefficient (function of time). The dipole moment $q(x)$ is obtained by multiplying the corresponding triangle surface by the dipole moment surface density of the cerebral cortex. This density is the product of the neocortical thickness (set to a constant value of 3 mm) and the cortical current surface density (100 nA/mm² for a normal background activity, see (Hamalainen and Sarvas, 1989)). The weighting coefficient $\alpha(t)$ represents

time-course of the dipole intensity and is provided by the output of the neuronal population model described in 2.1.

Figure 18: Spatio-temporal source model. A) T1-weighted 3D-MRI data were obtained from subject Colin Holmes, scanned 27 times at the Brain Imaging Center (MNI, Montreal, Canada). Scans were coregistered and averaged to get a high resolution (voxel size 1mm^3) anatomical dataset. This average was then spatially normalized in the MNI Talairach space to create the MRI volume called “colin27”, downloaded, for the purpose of our study, from <http://imaging.mrcmbu.cam.ac.uk/imaging/MniTalairach>. These data were segmented and triangulated using the BrainVisa software (IFR49, SHFJ, Orsay, France). The resulting mesh (grey-white matter interface) is composed of 210054 elementary triangles with a mean surface of 1mm^2 . (B) Each triangle is assumed to represent a neuronal population. The electrical contribution of each neuronal population is represented by an elementary current dipole, placed at the barycentre of the triangle and oriented orthogonally to triangle surface. The moment of each current dipole is weighted by both the triangle area and the population time-varying field activity or “population dynamics” (Cosandier-Rimele et al., 2008). This field activity is obtained from the model of neuronal populations described in section 2.1.

2.2.2 Representing a realistic coupling between cortical regions

In our model, the neuronal populations placed all over the cortical surface are coupled via excitatory connections between pyramidal cells, as reported in the literature (see section 2.1.2). This coupling should reflect the anatomical connections between cortical regions. Obviously, these connections are not distributed homogeneously in the brain, and follow a complex topology. This aspect is a key point as short- or long range connections (even for distant anatomical regions) constitute the substrate of physiological EEG rhythms. Accordingly, the realistic simulation of EEG signals implies that these rhythms can be reproduced i.e that a realistic coupling scheme between populations can be established.

2.2.2.1 The human connectome

Recently, a large scale study called “Human Connectome” was initiated at the Indiana University (Sporns et al., 2005) with the collaboration of the Department of Radiology at the University Hospital Center and University of Lausanne. As a result, the authors provided a map of anatomical connections linking human brain regions, called “connection matrix” (Hagmann et al., 2008; Hagmann et al., 2007).

In brief this matrix was obtained from analysing anatomical data in 5 normal subjects. The procedure they followed is detailed in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Extraction of a Whole Brain Structural Connectivity Network. (1) High-resolution T1 weighted and diffusion spectrum MRI (DSI) is acquired. DSI is represented with a zoom on the axial slice of the reconstructed diffusion map, showing an orientation distribution function at each position represented by a deformed sphere whose radius codes for diffusion intensity. Blue codes stand for the head-feet, red ones for left-right, and green ones for anterior-posterior orientations. (2) White and gray matter segmentation is performed from the T1-weighted image. (3a) 66 cortical regions with clear anatomical landmarks are created and then (3b) individually subdivided into small regions of interest (ROIs) resulting in 998 ROIs. (4) Whole brain tractography is performed providing an estimate of axonal trajectories across the entire white matter. (5) ROIs identified in step (3b) are combined with result of step (4) in order to compute the connection weight between each pair of ROIs. The result is a weighted network of structural connectivity across the entire brain. (Hagmann et al., 2008). For this report, permission has not been requested.

For each subject, the MRI data is segmented, and processed with sulci-recognition and automatic regional labelling algorithms to get a set of 66 anatomical regions covering both hemispheres. This partition is refined afterwards into about 1000 regions of interest (ROIs) that are combined with the axonal trajectories across the entire white matter, estimated from whole brain tractography.

As a next step, fiber densities for all pairs of ROIs are first averaged within each subregion and then across all five participants (see Figure 20). The obtained matrix represents the *connection weights* between the 66 regions defined according to anatomical landmarks.

Figure 20: Average Regional Connection Matrix, Network Layout, and Connectivity Backbone. (A) Matrix of inter-regional fiber densities between pairs of anatomical subregions, obtained by averaging over fiber densities for all pairs of ROIs within the regions, and averaging across all five participants. Connection weights are symmetric and are plotted on a logarithmic scale. **(B)** Network layout. **(C)** Dorsal and medial views of the connectivity backbone in anatomical coordinates. (Hagmann et al., 2008). For this report, permission has not been requested.

2.2.2.2 From the human connectome to the generation of brain dynamics

The connection matrix provided in Hagmann et al., constitute the element that was missing in our previous brain model (Cosandier-Rimele et al., 2007; Cosandier-Rimele et al., 2008). This element allows for realistic coupling of human cerebral regions.

In order to make use of this connection matrix for our data, we first needed to define on our mesh a similar set of 66 regions (33 per hemisphere) as those used in the “human connectome” study. To proceed, we used the Paraview software (version 3.4.0, www.paraview.org) to manually outline these regions on the grey/white interface mesh. Contiguous triangles belonging to each of the 66 regions were referenced in individual ROI files (see Figure 21).

RAC = rostral anterior cingulate cortex,
CAC = caudal anterior cingulate cortex,
PC = posterior cingulate cortex,
ISTC = isthmus of the cingulate cortex,

FP = frontal pole,
SF = superior frontal cortex,
RMF = rostral middle frontal cortex,
CMF = caudal middle frontal cortex,
POPE = pars opercularis,
PORB = pars orbitalis,
PTRI = pars triangularis,
LOF = lateral orbitofrontal cortex,
MOF = medial orbitofrontal cortex,

PREC = precentral gyrus,
PARC = paracentral lobule,
PSTS = postcentral gyrus,
SP = superior parietal cortex,
IP = inferior parietal cortex,
SMAR = supramarginal gyrus,
PCUN = precuneus,
LOCC = lateral occipital cortex,
CUN = cuneus,
PCAL = pericalcarine cortex,
LING = lingual gyrus,

ENT = entorhinal cortex,
PARH = parahippocampal cortex,
FUS = fusiform gyrus,
IT = inferior temporal cortex,
MT = middle temporal cortex,
ST = superior temporal cortex,
TP = temporal pole,
TT = transverse temporal cortex,
BSTS = bank of the superior temporal sulcus.

Figure 21: Outlined ROIs on our mesh. The exhaustive list of regions is given on the left of the figure. Contiguous triangles that belong to a same anatomical region are represented in a same color.

The next step will consist in generating the “neocortical dynamics” before solving the forward problem from these dynamics to the scalp electrodes and thus, getting the simulated scalp EEG data.

This step is still to be performed and will be the topic of short-term future work.

In practice, in our calculation of EEG signals, we will not consider one temporal dynamics for one triangle/dipole of the mesh as the complexity is too high. Instead, and to begin with, we plan to assign the same temporal dynamics to all triangles of a given anatomical region (see Figure 22). Indeed, it can be hypothesized that the activity that takes place over a given cortical region is “more or less” homogenous.

Therefore, we will need to generate from a model consisting in 66 coupled neuronal populations (as described in section 2.1) a set of 66 temporal dynamics. The coupling parameters (called K_{ij} in our model) will be defined as the elements of the 66×66 connection matrix from Hagmann et al. in order to account for anatomical coupling between brain regions.

Figure 22: From the “human connectome” to realistic brain dynamics. The model of neocortical populations introduced in 2.1 will be used along with coupling parameters between anatomical regions established by Hagmann et al. 2008 to generate 66 temporal dynamics. Each of them will be assigned to all dipoles in a given anatomical region before computing the forward problem.

2.2.3 Computation of electrical potentials on scalp electrodes (forward problem)

2.2.3.1 Basic principles

When modeling brain electrical fields, the quasistatic approximation is appropriate, i.e. propagation effects are negligible and there is no time-lag between electrical potentials at any point in the head and the underlying activity (Plonsey and Heppner, 1967). Moreover, we assumed the sources of the EEG to be current dipoles with fixed locations and orientations. Therefore, the relationship between sources and electrical potentials measured at sensors can be expressed by the following linear equation:

$$\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{G} \mathbf{I}$$

In this equation \mathbf{V} is the $M \times T$ data matrix (electrical potentials at scalp electrodes, relative to a point at infinity), \mathbf{G} is the $M \times N$ gain matrix, and \mathbf{I} is the $N \times T$ matrix of the time-varying intensities of the dipoles (M : number of electrodes, N : number of current dipoles and T : number of time samples).

The intensity matrix \mathbf{I} is determined by the temporal dynamics obtained from the population model. At each discrete time $t=j$ ($j=1, \dots, T$), I_{ij} gives the intensity of the i th dipole ($i=1, \dots, N$) at location x_i .

The gain matrix \mathbf{G} relates the set of the N current dipoles to the set of the potentials measured at the M sensors. Each coefficient G_{ki} of \mathbf{G} indicates the contribution of the i th dipole (with unit intensity) to the potential at the k^{th} sensor ($k=1, \dots, M$). It is obtained by solving the forward problem, i.e. by computing the electrical potential for a given source in the brain. To achieve this, a head model that provides a description of the shape and conductivity of the brain, the skull and the scalp is required. The electrical potentials at any point in the head can then be computed from standard physics equations (Poisson's equation).

2.2.3.2 Realistic head model and forward calculations

As the locations of scalp electrodes strongly depend on the head shape we built a realistic head model from the same 3D MRI data as the one used to create the cortical mesh. This model consists in three nested homogeneous compartments (brain, skull and scalp). As illustrated in Figure 23A, surface boundaries between the three tissues are extracted from the 3D MRI using segmentation tools (opening, dilatation, closing) implemented in the ASA software (ANT, Enschede, Netherlands). Each mesh (brain, skull and scalp) is obtained after triangulation (Figure 23B). Compared to the mesh used for the source model, a lower resolution is sufficient to approximate the shape of volume conductors. Therefore, each mesh is made of 2440 triangles.

According to the literature, the conductivity values of the brain and scalp are set to 0.33 S/m, and skull conductivity is assumed to be 40 times lower (Goncalves et al., 2003).

In a realistically shaped model, the forward calculations cannot be performed analytically. They must be performed using a numerical method. The potentials recorded on the scalp surface will be computed using the boundary element method (BEM) implemented in the ASA software (ANT, Enschede, Netherlands). This method is based on the isolated problem approach and has initially been described in (Hamalainen and Sarvas, 1989; Meijs et al., 1989).

Figure 23: Head model. A) segmentation of the brain, skull and scalp is performed on the colin27 MRI data using the software ASA3 (ANT, The Netherlands). B) Each mesh obtained after triangulation of the surface boundaries between the three tissues comprises 2240 triangles. C) The head model used for the forward calculation is made of the 3 nested meshes. On the outer surface of the scalp, 80 electrodes positions were defined following the extended 10-10 system.

3 CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

During this first year, progress has been accomplished on models describing the impact of current on neocortical tissue (local level) and on brain neurodynamics (global level).

As far as the impact of currents at local level is concerned, a neural mass model was developed based on a literature review about the cyto-architecture of the cerebral cortex. In this model, we studied a first scenario reproducing the effect of electrical stimulation only affecting the main cells (pyramidal neurons).

According to this scenario, we examined some necessary conditions in this model to reproduce the real signals recorded in rabbits by UPO. We found some model configurations that lead to the simulation of signals resembling actual responses.

Although it is still at an early stage, we think that the model could provide insights about: i) the respective contribution of the subpopulations of cells to the evoked response, ii) the effect of the stimulation on main cells and on interneurons and iii) the interpretation of real responses with respect to stimulation parameters. Therefore, this model should contribute to a major issue of HIVE: better understanding the response of cortical circuits to externally-applied electric field induced by direct stimulation of the cortex.

Regarding the perspectives on this part of the work, these preliminary results should be confirmed with the help of an accurate processing of real data recorded by UPO in the cerebral cortex of the rabbit. In particular, a characterization of cortical responses (positive and negative peaks, amplitude and corresponding latencies) is required for all experiments in which stimulation parameters are varied. This characterization will be used to validate the simulation results. Another exciting perspective would be to test experimentally some model predictions by selective blockade of synaptic receptors, for instance.

As far as the modeling of neurodynamics in the human brain is concerned, we have defined a strategy based on the extension of a previously published model that will allow us to account for the main neocortical regions in the human brain and for the connectivity among these regions, as recently published as the “human connectome”.

In this realistic representation, the activity of neocortical sources can be influenced by externally-applied electric fields as computed by models developed by FFCUL.

Our perspective is to solve the EEG forward problem in order to simulate electrical potentials generated at the surface of the head.

Therefore, such a model should predict some changes occurring in the EEG in response to stimulation effects occurring at the level of intracerebral sources.

Another major issue of HIVE is: better understanding the interaction between the brain activity (as reflected in the EEG) and electric fields induced by tDCS or TMS.

REFERENCES

- Bacci A, Rudolph U, Huguenard JR, Prince DA. 2003. Major differences in inhibitory synaptic transmission onto two neocortical interneuron subclasses. *J Neurosci* 23(29):9664-74.
- Banks MI, White JA, Pearce RA. 2000. Interactions between distinct GABA(A) circuits in hippocampus. *Neuron* 25(2):449-57.
- Bartos M, Vida I, Frotscher M, Meyer A, Monyer H, Geiger JR, Jonas P. 2002. Fast synaptic inhibition promotes synchronized gamma oscillations in hippocampal interneuron networks. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 99(20):13222-7.
- Bartos M, Vida I, Jonas P. 2007. Synaptic mechanisms of synchronized gamma oscillations in inhibitory interneuron networks. *Nat Rev Neurosci* 8(1):45-56.
- Bikson M, Inoue M, Akiyama H, Deans JK, Fox JE, Miyakawa H, Jefferys JG. 2004. Effects of uniform extracellular DC electric fields on excitability in rat hippocampal slices in vitro. *J Physiol* 557(Pt 1):175-90.
- Bojak I, Liley DT. 2005. Modeling the effects of anesthesia on the electroencephalogram. *Phys Rev E Stat Nonlin Soft Matter Phys* 71(4 Pt 1):041902.
- Buzsaki G, Geisler C, Henze DA, Wang XJ. 2004. Interneuron Diversity series: Circuit complexity and axon wiring economy of cortical interneurons. *Trends Neurosci* 27(4):186-93.
- Cosandier-Rimele D, Badier JM, Chauvel P, Wendling F. 2007. A physiologically plausible spatio-temporal model for EEG signals recorded with intracerebral electrodes in human partial epilepsy. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng* 54(3):380-8.
- Cosandier-Rimele D, Merlet I, Badier JM, Chauvel P, Wendling F. 2008. The neuronal sources of EEG: modeling of simultaneous scalp and intracerebral recordings in epilepsy. *Neuroimage* 42(1):135-46.
- Deisz RA. 1999. The GABA(B) receptor antagonist CGP 55845A reduces presynaptic GABA(B) actions in neocortical neurons of the rat in vitro. *Neuroscience* 93(4):1241-9.
- Deuchars J, Thomson AM. 1995. Innervation of burst firing spiny interneurons by pyramidal cells in deep layers of rat somatomotor cortex: paired intracellular recordings with biocytin filling. *Neuroscience* 69(3):739-55.
- Freeman WJ. 1978. Models of the dynamics of neural populations. *Electroencephalogr Clin Neurophysiol Suppl*(34):9-18.
- Freund TF, Buzsaki G. 1996. Interneurons of the hippocampus. *Hippocampus* 6(4):347-470.
- Freund TF, Katona I. 2007. Perisomatic inhibition. *Neuron* 56(1):33-42.
- Galarreta M, Hestrin S. 2002. Electrical and chemical synapses among parvalbumin fast-spiking GABAergic interneurons in adult mouse neocortex. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 99(19):12438-43.
- Glickfeld LL, Roberts JD, Somogyi P, Scanziani M. 2009. Interneurons hyperpolarize pyramidal cells along their entire somatodendritic axis. *Nat Neurosci* 12(1):21-3.
- Goncalves SI, de Munck JC, Verbunt JP, Bijma F, Heethaar RM, Lopes da Silva F. 2003. In vivo measurement of the brain and skull resistivities using an EIT-based method and realistic models for the head. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng* 50(6):754-67.

- Hagmann P, Cammoun L, Gigandet X, Meuli R, Honey CJ, Wedeen VJ, Sporns O. 2008. Mapping the structural core of human cerebral cortex. *PLoS Biol* 6(7):e159.
- Hagmann P, Kurant M, Gigandet X, Thiran P, Wedeen VJ, Meuli R, Thiran JP. 2007. Mapping human whole-brain structural networks with diffusion MRI. *PLoS One* 2(7):e597.
- Haider B, McCormick DA. 2009. Rapid neocortical dynamics: cellular and network mechanisms. *Neuron* 62(2):171-89.
- Hamalainen MS, Sarvas J. 1989. Realistic conductivity geometry model of the human head for interpretation of neuromagnetic data. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng* 36(2):165-71.
- Jansen BH RV. 1995. Electroencephalogram and visual evoked potential generation in a mathematical model of coupled cortical columns. *Biol Cybern.* 73(4):357-366.
- Jansen BH ZG, Brandt ME. 1993. A neurophysiologically-based mathematical model of flash visual evoked potentials. *Biol Cybern.* 68(3):275-283.
- Jonas P, Bischofberger J, Fricker D, Miles R. 2004. Interneuron Diversity series: Fast in, fast out--temporal and spatial signal processing in hippocampal interneurons. *Trends Neurosci* 27(1):30-40.
- Juhasz C, Asano E, Shah A, Chugani DC, Batista CE, Muzik O, Sood S, Chugani HT. 2009. Focal decreases of cortical GABAA receptor binding remote from the primary seizure focus: what do they indicate? *Epilepsia* 50(2):240-50.
- Kidd FL, Isaac JT. 1999. Developmental and activity-dependent regulation of kainate receptors at thalamocortical synapses. *Nature* 400(6744):569-73.
- Krook-Magnuson E, Huntsman MM. 2007. The transience of interneuron circuit diversity just "sped" up. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 104(43):16723-4.
- Lopes da Silva FH, Hoeks A, Smits H, Zetterberg LH. 1974. Model of brain rhythmic activity. The alpha-rhythm of the thalamus. *Kybernetik* 15(1):27-37.
- Lopes da Silva FH, van Rotterdam A, Barts P, van Heusden E, Burr W. 1976. Models of neuronal populations: the basic mechanisms of rhythmicity. *Prog Brain Res* 45:281-308.
- Markram H, Toledo-Rodriguez M, Wang Y, Gupta A, Silberberg G, Wu C. 2004. Interneurons of the neocortical inhibitory system. *Nat Rev Neurosci* 5(10):793-807.
- Meijs JW, Weier OW, Peters MJ, van Oosterom A. 1989. On the numerical accuracy of the boundary element method. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng* 36(10):1038-49.
- Miles R, Toth K, Gulyas AI, Hajos N, Freund TF. 1996. Differences between somatic and dendritic inhibition in the hippocampus. *Neuron* 16(4):815-23.
- Olah S, Komlosi G, Szabadics J, Varga C, Toth E, Barzo P, Tamas G. 2007. Output of neurogliaform cells to various neuron types in the human and rat cerebral cortex. *Front Neural Circuits* 1:4.
- Overstreet LS, Jones MV, Westbrook GL. 2000. Slow desensitization regulates the availability of synaptic GABA(A) receptors. *J Neurosci* 20(21):7914-21.
- Pearce RA. 1993. Physiological evidence for two distinct GABAA responses in rat hippocampus. *Neuron* 10(2):189-200.
- Plonsey R, Heppner DB. 1967. Considerations of quasi-stationarity in electrophysiological systems. *Bull Math Biophys* 29(4):657-64.
- Silberberg G. 2008. Polysynaptic subcircuits in the neocortex: spatial and temporal diversity. *Curr Opin Neurobiol* 18(3):332-7.
- Somogyi P, Tamas G, Lujan R, Buhl EH. 1998. Salient features of synaptic organisation in the cerebral cortex. *Brain Res Brain Res Rev* 26(2-3):113-35.

- Sporns O, Tononi G, Kotter R. 2005. The human connectome: A structural description of the human brain. *PLoS Comput Biol* 1(4):e42.
- Suffczynski P, Kalitzin S, Lopes Da Silva FH. 2004. Dynamics of non-convulsive epileptic phenomena modeled by a bistable neuronal network. *Neuroscience* 126(2):467-84.
- Szabadics J, Tamas G, Soltesz I. 2007. Different transmitter transients underlie presynaptic cell type specificity of GABA_A,slow and GABA_A,fast. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 104(37):14831-6.
- Tamas G, Lorincz A, Simon A, Szabadics J. 2003. Identified sources and targets of slow inhibition in the neocortex. *Science* 299(5614):1902-5.
- Thomson AM, Deuchars J. 1997. Synaptic interactions in neocortical local circuits: dual intracellular recordings in vitro. *Cereb Cortex* 7(6):510-22.
- Thomson AM, Deuchars J, West DC. 1996. Neocortical local synaptic circuitry revealed with dual intracellular recordings and biocytin-filling. *J Physiol Paris* 90(3-4):211-5.
- Wang Y, Gupta A, Markram H. 1999. Anatomical and functional differentiation of glutamatergic synaptic innervation in the neocortex. *J Physiol Paris* 93(4):305-17.
- Wendling F, Bartolomei F, Bellanger JJ, Chauvel P. 2002. Epileptic fast activity can be explained by a model of impaired GABAergic dendritic inhibition. *Eur J Neurosci* 15(9):1499-508.
- Wendling F, Bellanger JJ, Bartolomei F, Chauvel P. 2000. Relevance of nonlinear lumped-parameter models in the analysis of depth-EEG epileptic signals. *Biol Cybern* 83(4):367-78.
- Wendling F, Chauvel P. 2008. Transition to ictal activity in Temporal Lobe Epilepsy: insights from macroscopic models, in « Computational Neuroscience in Epilepsy », Edited by Drs. Ivan Soltesz and Kevin Staley, Elsevier.
- Wendling F, Hernandez A, Bellanger JJ, Chauvel P, Bartolomei F. 2005. Interictal to ictal transition in human temporal lobe epilepsy: insights from a computational model of intracerebral EEG. *J Clin Neurophysiol* 22(5):343-56.
- White JA, Banks MI, Pearce RA, Kopell NJ. 2000. Networks of interneurons with fast and slow gamma-aminobutyric acid type A (GABA_A) kinetics provide substrate for mixed gamma-theta rhythm. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 97(14):8128-33.
- Wilson HR CJ. 1973. A mathematical theory of the functional dynamics of cortical and thalamic nervous tissue. *Kybernetik* 13:55-80.

**Appendix A: Technical Note TN00172 entitled “Single-neuron and
lumped model stimulation coupling”
G. Ruffini, STARLAB (March 26, 2009)**

Single-neuron and lumped model stimulation coupling

Author: G. Ruffini

Date: March 26, 2009

Project: Brain stimulation

Status: Internal

Abstract

The effect of stimulation at the neuron level when the gradient of the field can be ignored is not simply proportional to field strength, since neuron characteristics also play an important role in the coupling. In earlier TNs we defined the concept of “single-neuron excitation function” and provide a model for this reflecting the results of TN00162 and TN00163 ([Ruffini:2008aa, Ruffini:2009aa]), namely the dependence of excitation on field intensity and relative orientation. This model can be used to couple electric field models to neuronal ensembles. We implement this excitation function into a simple single neuron model, showing it can alter the firing rate of the neuron in the expected manner. We describe in more detail the logic for the implementation of stimulation effects in the cable equation and provide some simulations and the code. The code is currently implemented for the biophysics of a squid. The next steps are to move to the mammalian case and also to implement the two compartment model discussed.

In addition, a two compartment model with coupling is described at the theoretical level.

Finally, we analyze coupling to a lumped model and provide the coupling recipe. We conclude that lumped models are applicable to the HIVE stimulation context. However, JIVE microscopic models and results should be used to tune the parameters of the population elements. It is best summarized by the following steps, starting from the input firing rate x , to the potential wave y and back out to the output firing rate.

$$\boxed{x_{\text{in}}(t) \xrightarrow{h(t)} y(t) \xrightarrow{\lambda_e \cdot E} y_E(t) \xrightarrow{S[y_E]} x_{\text{out}}(t)}$$

with $y_E(t) = y(t) + \lambda_e \cdot E(t)$.

Contents

1	Modified cable equation to account for termination	3
1.1	The algorithm	3
1.2	Code and sample simulations	5
1.3	Two-compartment model	7
1.4	In which direction?	11
2	From single neuron to lumped model coupling	16
2.1	Applicability of lumped models	16
2.2	From input firing rate to potential wave	17
2.3	From potential wave back to firing rate	17
3	Conclusions	20
4	Annex: Matlab code	21
4.1	Batch file: batchspikingprobability.m	21
4.2	Main file: starspikev8.m	22
4.3	Peak finder: StarPeakFinder.m	27

1 Modified cable equation to account for termination

1.1 The algorithm

In this section we detail the algorithm implemented. The actual equations that go into the code have an equation number. The parameters used in the simulation are those below, with the exception of the resting potentials (we use Trappenberg's convention).

For an active membrane the equation has to be modified to represent the effect of a termination. As discussed in [Bower:2003aa] we have the compartmental version of the cable equation already considering stimulation by direct current injection,

$$\frac{V_m'' - V_m}{R_i} - \frac{V_m - V_m'}{R_i} + I_{inject} = C_m \frac{dV_m}{dt} + \sum_k g_k(V_m) (V_m - E_k)$$

where all the relevant resistances are considered in the sum (including leakage). The effect of stimulation can be thought of as an instantaneous perturbation of the transmembrane potential.

The natural units are mV, ms, KOhm, uF, cm and combinations of these (e.g., the field is in mV/cm).

We now need to use active membrane parameters to compute the equivalent injected current by the stimulation. Let us define the total conductance and resistance as

$$g_T(V_m) = \sum_k g_k(V_m), \quad R_m^T(V_m) = 1/g_T(V_m) \quad (1.1)$$

Using this total voltage dependent resistance we now define $r_m^T(V_m)$ (resistance times length) in the usual way. Let δ be the membrane thickness and L compartment length. Then we relate the resistance to "per length" versions,

$$R_m^T = \rho_m \frac{\delta}{2\pi a L} \equiv \frac{r_m^T}{L}; \quad r_m^T = L R_m^T = \rho_m \frac{\delta}{2\pi a}$$

while

$$R_i = \rho_i \frac{L}{\pi a^2} \equiv r_i L; \quad r_i = \frac{R_i}{L} = \frac{\rho_i}{\pi a^2}$$

and

$$\lambda(V_m) = \sqrt{\frac{r_m^T}{r_i}} = L \sqrt{\frac{R_m^T}{R_i}} = \sqrt{a \frac{\delta \rho_m}{2 \rho_i}}, \quad \tau_m(V_m) = r_T(V_m) c_m$$

Let us also define the membrane conductance and resistance as a function of membrane area (the ones used in the table below and in the code):

$$r'_m = \rho_m \delta = R_m^T 2\pi a L \equiv \frac{1}{g'_m} \quad [\text{with units } \text{k}\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2] \quad (1.2)$$

Then

$$\lambda = \sqrt{\frac{r'_m}{2\rho_i/a}} \quad (1.3)$$

We recall that the effect of an electric field in a termination is to displace the transmembrane potential by an amount $\lambda \cdot E$ (see [Ruffini:2009aa]). Using this total resistance and associated space and time “constants” we now write

$$I_{inject} \approx I_n(t) + \lambda(V_m) \cdot E/R_m^T$$

and its density (per area) version

$$J_{inject} \approx J_n(t) + \lambda(V_m) \cdot E/r'_m \quad (1.4)$$

where we revert to current density and resistance times area (natural experimental units).

The first term, $I_n(t)$ refers to current injected by another neuron (e.g., a current pulse: this is the typical term found in HH simulations). The second term corresponds to the (TMS or tDCS) stimulation coupling: the membrane polarization term in the termination situation is $\lambda \cdot E$ and the current flow will be inversely proportional to membrane resistance. We can see that when channels open and conductivity increases, both space and time constants decrease. The impact of the stimulating field decreases during that time.

What the second term is saying is that the stimulation, which leads to a transmembrane potential of $\lambda \cdot E$ (dot product in general) is equivalent to stimulation by a transmembrane current of $I_s \equiv \lambda(V_m) \cdot E/R_m^T$. This is immediate, as the transmembrane current is proportional to the transmembrane potential divided by the (instantaneous) transmembrane resistance.

We expect to see action potential initiation if E is relatively large (TMS) and neuromodulation if smaller (tDCS).

We will now limit the discussion to a single compartment, since we want to focus on a termination or bend. The equation becomes a modified HH equation:

$$I_n + \frac{\lambda(V_m)E}{R_m^T} = C_m \frac{dV_m}{dt} + \sum_k g_k(V_m) (V_m - E_k)$$

or (dropping for convenience some subscripts)

$$I_n R_m^T + \lambda(V)E = \tau_m(V) \frac{dV}{dt} + \sum_k \frac{g_k(V_m)}{g_T(V)} (V_m - E_k)$$

We now drop reference to the compartment model, since there is no reference to L anymore. The conductances can be referred to their “per area” definition, etc.

For the code implementation we will use the current density version of the cable equation

$$J_n + \frac{\lambda(V_m)E}{r'_m} = c_m \frac{dV_m}{dt} + \sum_k g'_k(V_m) (V_m - E_k) \quad (1.5)$$

(with c_m the capacitance per unit area, $c_m = C_m/(2\pi aL)$ in the form

$$\begin{aligned} V_m(t + dt) &\approx V_m(t) + \frac{dV_m}{dt} dt \\ &= V_m(t) + \frac{1}{c_m} \left(J_n + \frac{\lambda(V_m)E}{r'_m} - \sum_k g'_k(V_m) (V_m - E_k) \right) dt \end{aligned} \quad (1.6)$$

The HH conductance/voltage equation are

$$g'_{Na} = \bar{g}_{Na} m^3 h, \quad g'_K = \bar{g}_K n^4, \quad g'_L = \bar{g}_L \quad (1.7)$$

(and $g'_T = g'_{Na} + g'_K + g'_L$) with

$$\dot{m} = \alpha_m(V)(1 - m) - \beta_m(V)m, \quad (1.8)$$

$$\dot{h} = \alpha_h(V)(1 - h) - \beta_h(V)h,$$

$$\dot{n} = \alpha_n(V)(1 - n) - \beta_n(V)n.$$

and

$$\alpha_m = \frac{0.1(-40 - V)}{\exp(\frac{-40 - V}{10}) - 1.0} \quad (1.9)$$

$$\beta_m = 4.0 \exp(\frac{-65 - V}{18})$$

$$\alpha_h = 0.07 \exp(\frac{-65 - V}{20})$$

$$\beta_h = \frac{1.0}{\exp(\frac{-35 - V}{10}) + 1.0}$$

$$\alpha_n = \frac{0.01(-55 - V)}{\exp(\frac{-55 - V}{10}) - 1.0}$$

$$\beta_n = 0.125 \exp(\frac{-65 - V}{80})$$

(1.10)

In [Rattay:1998aa] it is suggested to multiply the rates for the gating variables by 12 to account for faster gating processes in mammalian neurons.

Table 1 – HH parameters from [Roth:1990aa] Table I

E_{Na}	Sodium Nerst Potential	50.0 mV
E_K	Potassium Nerst Potential	-77.0 mV
E_L	Leakage Nerst Potential	-54.387 mV
\bar{g}'_{Na}	Sodium conductance	120.0 mmho/cm ²
\bar{g}'_K	Potassium conductance	36.0 mmho/cm ²
\bar{g}'_L	Leakage conductance	0.3 mmho/cm ²
c_m	Membrane capacitance per area	1.0 μ F /cm ²
ρ_i	Resistivity of axoplasm	0.0354 k Ω ·cm
a	Fiber radius	0.0238 cm

1.2 Code and sample simulations

In this section we report some results of simulation using the above recipe for coupling.

The code models the single compartment models described above. For this purpose we have adapted code in [Trappenberg:2002aa] in Table 12.2 (file hh.m), now modified extensively.

In terms of the **units** used we have :

- J, current density in $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$
- V, Voltage in mV
- a, lengths in cm
- E field, in mV/cm
- Time in ms
- cm, Capacitance per unit area in $\mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$
- Resistance times unit area in kOhm cm^2
- Etc: mV, cm, ms, kOhm, μF

The code has the following **input parameters**:

- Currentcode: 'Jrandom', 'Jconstant', 'Jperiodicpulse', 'Jsine'
- J_extM: max external current density in uA per cm2
- Jperiodms: periodic stimulation interval in ms. Not used in Jrandom
- Jpulsedurationms: pulse duration in ms (only for random or pulsed cases, otherwise use 0)
- Stimulationcode: 'Erandom', 'Econstant', 'Eperiodicpulse', 'Esine'
- E_extM: max external field in mV per cm
- Eperiodms: periodic stimulation interval in ms. Not used in Erandom
- Epulsedurationms: pulse duration in ms (only for random or pulsed cases, otherwise use 0)

The code **outputs** are:

- time step array [t], in ms
- membrane voltage [V], mV
- $\lambda * E/r$ term arrays [λEr]; A
- Number of spikes [N]

In addition, the code generates the following **side effects**:

- Figure is created showing $V(t)$ and $\lambda E(t)/r'$
- PDF figure is created in working directory.

The code is composed of several files:

- starspikev8: this is the main code
- StarPeakFinder, which is called by the main and which identifies peaks in time series, and
- batchspikingprobability, a batch file calling the main code to produce results for a range of frequencies.

As an **example**, copy the code into a directory, change directory to this directory, and execute

```
[ t,V,lambdaE,N]=starspikev8('Jconstant',3,0,0, 'Eperiodicpulse', 7.5, 1,19);
```

This calls the main code with a constant injected current density of magnitude 3 ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$), and with a pulsed E field of magnitude 7.5 mV/cm, 1 ms of pulse duration and 19 ms repetition period. This happens to be a resonant frequency.

1.3 Two-compartment model

In [Park:2005aa] (p.2) the authors state that the presence of external fields causes a spatial polarization of neurons, and therefore that the use of at least two compartment models is 'mandatory'. For a two compartment model (one somatic, the other dendritic), we have the following coupled two equations

$$\frac{V_D - V_S}{R_i} + I_S^s = C_m \frac{dV_S}{dt} + \sum_k g_k(V_S) (V_S - E_S^k)$$

and

$$\frac{V_S - V_D}{R_i} + I_D^s = C_m \frac{dV_D}{dt} + \sum_k g_k(V_D) (V_D - E_D^k)$$

where now we account for current transfer between the two compartments in the current conservation law. If we now model the dentrite's membrane as passive, and allow for current injection only at the dendrite, we can write

$$\frac{V_D - V_S}{R_i} + \frac{\lambda_S(V_S) \cdot E}{R_m^T(V_S)} = C_m \frac{dV_S}{dt} + \sum_k g_k(V_S) (V_S - E_S^k)$$

and

$$\frac{V_S - V_D}{R_i} + I_D^s - \frac{\lambda_D(V_D) \cdot E}{R_m^T(V_D)} = C_m \frac{dV_D}{dt} + g_r(V_D) (V_D - E_D^r)$$

where we assume opposite orientations for soma and dendritic compartments. The constants for these equations need to be carefully defined before proceeding (to be discussed with Albert).

Thus, as a baseline, we will consider that 1) the dendrite is passive (only a leakage current will be allowed), 2) the external current is injected in the dendrite only, and 3) that the stimulation effects will be different for dendrite and soma (depending on the spatial parameter and orientation/sign). E.g., if the dendrite depolarizes, the soma should hyperpolarize.

For implementation using Euler's method we can rewrite these two equations as

$$V_S(t + dt) \approx V_S(T) + dt \frac{dV_S}{dt} =$$

$$V_S(T) + dt \frac{1}{C_m} \left(\frac{V_D - V_S}{R_i} + \frac{\lambda_S(V_S) \cdot E}{R_m^T(V_S)} - \sum_k g_k(V_S) (V_S - E_S^k) \right)$$

and

$$V_D(t + dt) \approx V_D(T) + dt \frac{dV_D}{dt} =$$

$$V_D(T) + dt \frac{1}{C_m} \left(\frac{V_S - V_D}{R_i} + I_D^s - \frac{\lambda_D(V_D) \cdot E}{R_m^T(V_D)} - g_r(V_D) (V_D - E_D^r) \right)$$

Figure 1 – Top: simulation at a non-resonant frequency; Middle: sub-fundamental resonance; Bottom: resonant frequency. Stimulation intensity is constant throughout.

Figure 2 – Simulations results for a range of stimulation periods showing resonance phenomena at a fundamental and harmonic frequency ($2f$). In the y axis the spike probability is provided (total number of spikes divided by total number of stimulation pulses).

1.4 In which direction?

In previous work ([Ruffini:2009ac] and references therein) we have stated that λ should point from dendritic tuft to soma, so that ‘orthodromic’ fields (i.e., pointing in the same direction) are excitatory based on the intuition that what happens at the soma is key. However, in a two compartment model we have antagonistic effects at dendrite and soma.

Here we review a bit more some of the literature to check our intuition. [Bikson:2004aa] states that a negative field increases excitability. In his convention, this means orthodromic stimulation, with the field pointing in the direction dendrite-to-soma. Thus, this work agrees with the ‘orthodromic’ proposal made, and it shows that even if the effects of the field are opposite in the dendrite and soma, what is important is what happens at the soma—see Figure 4.

[Park:2005aa] (p.2) states that the presence of external fields causes a spatial polarization of neurons, and therefore that the use of at least two compartment models is ‘mandatory’. The spatial aspect of polarization is evident (see for example Figure 5). Moreover, it does appear, based on our early results, that the two compartment model is adding a layer of phenomena that is missing in the single compartment. For instance, early results show that the relation of field intensity to firing rate is not monotonic.

We conclude that the orthodromic conjecture is correct, but that a single compartment model will need to use an adapted value for this parameter to, e.g., match the results of a two compartment one, and that there are phenomena that escape the single compartment model and which may be very important. More on this when the IDIBAPS team obtains results on the two compartment model.

Figure 3 – Hippocampus anatomy (top) and connections (bottom)

Figure 4 – Excerpt from figure 7 of [Bikson:2004aa]. In this paper ‘positive fields’ are in the soma-to-dendrite direction. They are soma-hyperpolarizing, while ‘negative’ fields (which we have called ‘orthodromic’), in the dendrite-to-soma direction, are depolarizing and therefore excitatory. This shows that the relevant aspect to consider is what happens at the soma. The soma rules.

Figure 5 – Pyramidal-like neuron shaper response to an external field.

Figure 6 – Pyramidal-like neuron shape response to an external field.

2 From single neuron to lumped model coupling

2.1 Applicability of lumped models

We begin our analysis here of how to translate the proposed single neuron coupling model to the ‘lumped’ population models as described in [Wendling:2008aa, Jansen:1993aa, Jansen:1995aa], and very lucidly in [Grimbert:2005aa].

The first point to be made is that the lumped model is a firing rate model [Dayan:2001aa], although it is mathematically described in terms of an average membrane potential for the populations. That is, the internal degrees of freedom of the lumped neuron are represented by the membrane potential (in the model, y_0 , y_1 , and y_2). The h functions (kernels), transform firing rates into membrane potential waves. Those add up and are then transformed back into firing rates. Thus, their action of this ‘pulse-to-wave’ kernels is a linear transformation and their effects can in fact be represented by linear differential equations (in this case, second order). Basically, they implement a low pass filter. The resulting potentials are then transformed back into firing rates through the use of a sigmoid ‘wave-to-pulse’ function.

A point to consider with regards to modeling stimulation is to check if there are any issues associated to this level of modeling in relation to our projects. In particular, since it is known that firing rate models do not account for precise pulse timing aspects, the lumped model will *fail to describe a network adequately if the presynaptic inputs of a substantial fraction of its neurons are correlated ... this will occur, e.g., if the presynaptic neurons fire synchronously* [Dayan:2001aa, p. 231].

This is an important concern, because with the stimulation schemes we are working with, stimulation is certainly coherent (synchronous) at the population level: all the neurons in a population experience the stimulation in synch (e.g., if we are thinking of tACS). We may make here a distinction between HIVE and JIVE.

Lumped models should be applicable to HIVE. This is because the stimulation paradigms we are interested in to study in this project are ‘large scale’ and ‘slow time’. As long as the time scales (spectra) of the electrical stimulation we are concerned about are long in comparison to inter-pulse times, ‘coherence’ aspects that affect different populations regions will be consistently included in the lumped model. We can therefore still model AC stimulation at different brain regions with definite frequency and phase relation with a lumped model, as long as the frequencies involved are low compared to firing rates. But the effect of such fields at the single population level needs further analysis. For example, as pointed out in [Trappenberg:2002aa, p. 75, section 4.3.4], lumped models need to use very small time constants (much shorter than typical membrane ones) in order to reproduce the response of microscopic models to rapid, coherent, stimulus—see Figure 7.

In addition, some of the sensitivity amplification (resonance) work we have considered falls clearly in the realm of JIVE (where synchrony should be relevant for weak field sensitivity [Francis:2003aa]), and it should be modeled with the microscopic model.

It should then be clear that it will be key to use microscopic models to ‘tune’ the single population lumped model under stimulation.

In summary, lumped models are applicable to HIVE. JIVE microscopic models and results should be used to tune the parameters of the population elements.

2.2 From input firing rate to potential wave

In more detail, in the lumped model the post synaptic transform converts an average firing frequency into an electric potential through a second order differential linear transform whose equivalent impulse response is given by $h(t) = Aat \exp[-at]$ for $t \geq 0$ [Grimbert:2005aa]

$$\ddot{y} = aAx(t) - 2a\dot{y} - a^2y(t)$$

where $x(t)$ is the average input firing rate, and $y(t)$ the average membrane potential perturbation. Different constants a and A are used for inhibitory and excitatory neurons.

2.3 From potential wave back to firing rate

To convert the potential time series into an output firing rate, a sigmoid function is used

$$S(y_i) = \frac{2e_0}{1 + \exp[r(V_0 - y_i)]}$$

The effect of an external electric field in these models, then, will be taken into consideration as a shift in the membrane potential. That is, we will change the wave-to-pulses function by

$$S_E(y_i) = \frac{2e_0}{1 + \exp[r(V_0 - \lambda_e \cdot E - y_i)]}, \quad (2.1)$$

Figure 7 – Figure from [Trappenberg:2002aa, p. 75, section 4.3.4], highlighting the limitations of lumped models with regards to fast stimulation processes.

where the convention assumes once again ‘orthodromicity’, i.e., that an E field aligned with λ_e is here excitatory. The constant λ_e will require here some tuning as well, as it is a large scale effective one (as opposed to the microscopic one, λ).

In summary, we have provided a recipe to include an external electric field in the lumped model. It is best summarized by the following steps, starting from the input firing rate x , to the potential wave y and back out to the output firing rate.

$$\boxed{x_{\text{in}}(t) \xrightarrow{h(t)} y(t) \xrightarrow{\lambda_e \cdot E} y_E(t) \xrightarrow{S[y_E]} x_{\text{out}}(t)}$$

with

$$y_E(t) = y(t) + \lambda_e \cdot E(t).$$

Figure 8 – Top: Figure 8 from [Grimbert:2005aa]. “Model of a cortical column: if features a population of pyramidal cells interacting with two populations of inter-neurons, one excitatory (left branch) and the other inhibitory (right branch).” Bottom: Figure 9 from [Grimbert:2005aa]. Pulse to wave (h) and wave to pulse functions (Sigm) are represented, and y_0 , y_1 and y_2 represent therefore the population average membrane potential. “Model of a cortical column. The h boxes simulate synapses between the neurons populations. They perform a second order differential linear transformation that converts the average firing rate of the presynaptic population into a membrane potential of the post-synaptic one. The ‘Sigm’ boxes simulate cell bodies of neurons by transforming the membrane potential of a population into an output firing rate. This is a nonlinear transformation. The constants C_i model the strength of the synaptic connection between populations.”

3 Conclusions

In order to describe the effect of stimulation we have defined the concept of excitation function [Ruffini:2009aa], namely the dependence of excitation on field intensity and relative orientation. The basic physics of neuron-field interaction when field gradients can be ignored (as is probably the case in tDCS and TMS) is provided by the termination concept, and the perturbation of the membrane potential by a term proportional to the spatial constant and the electric field projected in a preferred direction. This model can be used to couple electric field models to neuronal ensembles, using imaging data to infer orientation fields.

Here we detail such a model and provided a code implementation in Matlab. This is a suitable starting point for integration into many neuron microscopic levels (as in [Compte:2008aa]).

For population models, the natural level of integration would be at the level of firing rate modulation. Since the effect appears to be rather similar to that of an injected current, earlier models and experimental results can be used.

Simple neuron simulations show that the proposed excitation coupling has the right properties, being capable of altering firing state and rate of a neuron. In vitro stimulation experiments could clarify the proper coupling excitation function, and investigate the observed resonance phenomena.

Finally, we conclude that despite their limitations lumped models are applicable to HIVE's large scale, low frequency stimulation paradigms, but that JIVE microscopic models and results should be used to tune the parameters of the population time constants and coupling.

4 Annex: Matlab code

4.1 Batch file: batchspikingprobability.m

```

1  %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
2  % Use this batch file to produce a series of simulations
3  % with starspikev8
4  % G. Ruffini, Starlab, Feb 25 2009
5  %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
6
7  %% Define current and stimulation types
8  Currentcode='Jconstant'; % options are 'Jrandom', 'Jconstant',
9  %'Jperiodicpulse', 'Jsine'
10 Stimulationcode='Eperiodicpulse'; % options are 'Erandom', 'Econstant',
11 %'Eperiodicpulse', 'Esine'
12
13 %% define current parameters
14 J_extM=3; % uA/cm2
15 Jperiodms=0; %ms
16 Jpulsedurationms=0; %ms
17
18 %% define E field stimulation parameters
19 E_extM=7; % mV/cm
20 Eperiodms = 3:0.5:32; % ms (an array here)
21 Epulsedurationms=1; %ms
22
23 %% compute the number of periods
24 N=Eperiodms;
25 Nstimpeaks=1000 ./Eperiodms; % this assumes that 1000 ms used in simulation
26 % this duration hardcoded in starspikev8
27
28 % run for loop for each parameter
29 figure(1)
30 for i=1:length(N) [ t,V,lambdaE,N(i)]= ...
31     starspikev8(Currentcode ,J_extM,Jpulsedurationms,Jperiodms, ...
32     Stimulationcode, E_extM, Epulsedurationms,Eperiodms(i));
33 end
34
35 %% plot the spiking probability
36 figure;
37 plot(Eperiodms, (N ./Nstimpeaks).*100, '*');
38 xlabel('Stimulus period (ms)');
39 ylabel('Approximate Spiking probability');
40 title(['I->constant A=' num2str(J_extM) ...
41     '; E->periodic pulses A=' num2str(E_extM) ' mV per cm, tau=' ...
42     num2str(Epulsedurationms) ' ms' ] );
43
44 %% create pdf file of the figure
45 printtitle=['SP J->constant: A=' num2str(J_extM) ...
46     '; E->periodic pulses A=' num2str(E_extM) ' mV per cm, tau=' ...
47     num2str(Epulsedurationms) ' ms.pdf'];
48 print( '-dpdf',printtitle); % create pdf file
49
50
51 starspikev8(Currentcode, J_extM, Jpulsedurationms, Jperiodms,...
52     Stimulationcode, E_extM, Epulsedurationms, Eperiodms)

```

4.2 Main file: starspikev8.m

```

1  function [ t_plot,V_plot, lambdaEr_plot,N]= ...
2      starspikev8(Currentcode, J_extM, Jpulsedurationms, Jperiodms,...
3          Stimulationcode, E_extM, Epulsedurationms, Eperiodms)
4  %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
5  % Integration of Hodgkin—Huxley equations with Euler method
6  % Based on Trappenger's hh.m function Table 12.2
7  % Modified to include external tDCS or TMS stimulation
8  % using a lambda*E stimulation perturbation term in the equation
9  % This version generalizes stim and "natural" current waveforms
10 % to allow for pulses or sinusoids
11 % Ref: TN00172 and references therein
12 % G. Ruffini, Starlab, Feb 22, 2009
13 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
14 %{
15
16 This code models the effect of termination type of stimulation
17 impact into a single compartment neuron model.
18
19 The logic is that the stimulation field leads to a transmembrane
20 potential perturbation of the order lambda E.
21 For more information see Starlab TN00172 and references therein.
22
23 Units:
24     J, current density in uA per cm2
25     V, Voltage in mV
26     a, lengths in cm
27     E field, in mV/cm
28     Time in ms
29     cm, Capacitance per area in uF/cm2
30     Resistance times area in kOhm cm2
31     Etc: mV, cm, ms, KOhm, uF
32
33 Inputs:
34     - Currentcode: 'Jrandom', 'Jconstant', 'Jperiodicpulse', 'Jsine'
35     - J_extM: max external current density in uA per cm2
36     - Jperiodms: periodic stimulation interval in ms. Unused in Jrandom
37     - Jpulsedurationms: pulse duration in ms
38       (only for random or pulsed cases, otherwise ignored)
39
40     - Stimulationcode: 'Erandom', 'Econstant', 'Eperiodicpulse', 'Esine'
41     - E_extM: max external field in mV per cm
42     - Eperiodms: periodic stimulation interval in ms. Not used in Erandom
43     - Epulsedurationms: pulse duration in ms
44       (only for random or pulsed cases, otherwise ignored)
45
46 *NB: not all parameters are needed in all the possible optional options.
47
48 In particular:
49
50     - Jrandom/Erandom require only J_extM/E_extM and
51       Jpulsedurationms/Epulsedurationms (not periods)
52     - Jconstant/Econstant requires only the magnitudes J_extM/E_extM
53     - Eperiodicpulse/Jperiodicpulse require all parameters
54     - Jsine/Esine require J_extM/E_extM and Jperiodms/Eperiodms

```



```

112     %%%%%%%%% J_ext: CHOOSE one of the following %%%%%%%%%%
113     %%%%%%%%%%
114     switch Currentcode
115
116         case 'Jrandom'
117     %1) for injected current density with random n pulses:
118         npulses=ceil((t2-t1)/Jpulsedurationms);
119         randoma=randint(npulses,1,[0,1]); % use for 0 and 1
120         ar= repmat(randoma,1,Jpulseduration)'; % replicate each pulse bit
121             %Jpulseduration times
122         J_ext=J_extM*reshape(ar, 1,npulses*Jpulseduration)'; % ext
123         J_ext=(J_ext-0.5*J_extM)*2; %biphasic, both pos and neg
124         Jcode=['J->random pulses A=' num2str(J_extM) ...
125             ' uA per cm2, tau=' num2str(Jpulsedurationms) ' ms']
126
127         case 'Jconstant'
128     %2) for a constant injected current density:
129         J_ext=J_extM* ones([iterations,1]);
130         Jcode = ['J->const A=' num2str(J_extM) ' uA per cm2' ]
131
132
133         case 'Jperiodicpulse'
134     %3) for a periodic injected current with square pulses:
135         interpulse=Jperiod-Jpulseduration;
136         onepulse=J_extM*[ones(1, Jpulseduration), zeros(1,interpulse)];
137         pulselength=length(onepulse);
138         J_ext= repmat(onepulse, 1, ceil(iterations/Jperiod));
139         Jcode=['J->periodic pulses A=' num2str(J_extM) ...
140             ' uA per cm2, tau=' num2str(Jpulsedurationms) ...
141             ' ms, Ts=' num2str(Jperiodms) ' ms']
142
143         case 'Jsine'
144     %4) for periodic injected current with sine wave;
145
146         J_ext =J_extM*sin(2*3.14* [1:iterations]/Jperiod);
147         Jcode = ['J->sine A=' num2str(J_extM) ...
148             ' uA per cm2, Ts=' num2str(Jperiodms)]
149
150         otherwise
151             disp('Unknown current injection method')
152     end
153
154     %%%%%%%%%%
155     %%%%%%%%%% E_ext: CHOOSE one of the following %%%%%%%%%%
156     %%%%%%%%%%
157     switch Stimulationcode
158
159         case 'Erandom'
160     %1) for random stimulation with npulses:
161
162         npulses=ceil((t2-t1)/Epulsedurationms);
163         randoma=randint(npulses,1,[0,1]); % use for 0 and 1
164         ar= repmat(randoma,1,Epulseduration)'; % replicate each pulse bit
165         E_ext=E_extM*reshape(ar, 1,npulses*Epulseduration)'; % ext
166         E_ext=(E_ext-0.5*E_extM)*2; %biphasic
167         Ecode=['E->random pulses A=' num2str(E_extM) ...
168             ' mV per cm, tau=' num2str(Epulsedurationms) ' ms']

```

```

169
170     case 'Econstant'
171 %2) for a constant field:
172     E_ext=E_extM* ones([iterations,1]);
173     Ecode = ['E->const A=' num2str(E_extM) ' mV per cm']
174
175     case 'Eperiodicpulse'
176
177 %3) for a periodic stimulation with square pulses:
178     interpulse=Eperiod-Epulseduration;
179     onepulse=E_extM*[ones(1, Epulseduration), zeros(1, interpulse)];
180     E_ext= repmat(onepulse, 1, ceil(iterations/Eperiod));
181     Ecode=['E->periodic pulses A=' num2str(E_extM) ' mV per cm, tau=' ...
182           num2str(Epulsedurationms) ' ms, Ts=' num2str(Eperiodms) ' ms']
183
184     case 'Esine'
185 %4) for periodic stimulation with sine wave;
186     E_ext=E_extM*sin(2*3.14* [1:iterations]/Eperiod);
187     Ecode = ['E->sine A=' num2str(E_extM) ' mV per cm, Ts=' ...
188             num2str(Eperiodms) ' ms']
189
190     otherwise
191         disp('Unknown method stimulation method')
192 end
193
194 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
195
196
197 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
198 %   T I M E   L O O P   —   I N T E G R A T I O N %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
199 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
200
201 % Integration with Euler method time loop
202 for i=1:iterations
203     t=i*dt +t1;
204
205 % alpha functions used by Hodgkin-and Huxley
206     alpha(1)=(10-V)/(100*(exp((10-V)/10)-1));
207     alpha(2)=(25-V)/(10*(exp((25-V)/10)-1));
208     alpha(3)=0.07*exp(-V/20);
209 % beta functions used by Hodgkin-and Huxley
210     beta(1)=0.125*exp(-V/80);
211     beta(2)=4*exp(-V/18);
212     beta(3)=1/(exp((30-V)/10)+1);
213 % Tau_x and x_0 are defined with alpha and beta
214     tau=1./(alpha+beta);
215     x_0=alpha.*tau;
216 % leaky integration with Euler method
217     x=(1-dt./tau).*x+dt./tau.*x_0;
218 % calculate actual conductances g with given n, m, h
219     gnmh(1)=g(1)*x(1)^4;
220     gnmh(2)=g(2)*x(2)^3*x(3);
221     gnmh(3)=g(3);
222
223 % see Eq (1.2) in TN00172
224     rprime=1/(gnmh(1)+gnmh(2)+gnmh(3)); % kOhm*cm2
225

```

```

226     % see Eq (1.3) in TN00172 for def of lambda (in cm here)
227     lambdaE=E_ext(i)*sqrt(rprime/(2*rhoi/a)); % in mV
228
229
230 % Ohm's law
231     J=gnmh.*(V-E); %mv/(kOhm cm2) or uA per cm2
232
233 % Now we update voltage of membrane
234 % V=V+dt*(J_ext(i)-sum(I)) was the original term in Trappenberg
235 % We correct this by addint the stimulation term as in TN00172 (1.6)
236 % adding stimulation and capacitance per unit area
237
238     V=V+dt*(J_ext(i)+lambdaE/rprime-sum(J))/cm; % stimulation added; mV
239
240 % record some variables for plotting after reaching steady state
241     if t>=0;
242         t_rec=t_rec+1;
243         t_plot(t_rec)=t;
244         V_plot(t_rec)=V;
245         J_plot(t_rec)=J_ext(i);
246         lambdaEr_plot(t_rec)=lambdaE/rprime;
247     end
248 end % time loop ends
249 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
250
251 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
252 %%% find the spikes and count how many there are %%%%%%%%%
253 nuV_plot=V_plot;
254 nuV_plot(nuV_plot<E(2)/2)=NaN;
255 nuV_plot(nuV_plot<max(nuV_plot)/1.5)=NaN;
256 peaks=StarPeakFinder(nuV_plot); % finds good spikes
257 N=length(peaks) % get and output number of peaks
258 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
259
260 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
261 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% Plot some the results %%%%%%%%%
262 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
263
264 figure(1)
265
266 plot(t_plot,V_plot); xlabel('Time (ms)');
267 ylabel('V (mV, blue), J_inj (red) & lambda*E/rprime (green, uA/cm2)');
268 hold on;
269
270 plot(t_plot,J_plot,'r');
271 plot(t_plot,lambdaEr_plot,'g') ;
272 plot(t_plot(peaks),nuV_plot(peaks),'*r');
273 plotlabel=[Jcode ' ' Ecode ' ==> N= ' num2str(N) ];
274 title(plotlabel);
275
276 % create PDF version of the plot
277 filetitle=[plotlabel '.pdf'];
278 print( '-dpdf',filetitle);
279 hold off;
280
281
282 end

```

4.3 Peak finder: StarPeakFinder.m

```
1 function peaks=StarPeakFinder(fx)
2
3 % This function finds local maxima.
4 % in at time series fx
5 % returns peak positions
6
7 % By Giulio Ruffini, June 2006
8 % Example
9 % % first condition is a high XCF
10 %     cXCF=XCF;
11 %     cXCF(XCF<max(XCF)/2)=NaN;
12 %     pos=StarPeakFinder(cXCF);
13
14 fx=reshape(fx,length(fx),1);
15 %fx(fx<max(fx)/2)=0;
16
17 differential=diff(fx);
18 %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% PEAK FINDER using 3 Conditions
19 posiciones=1:length(differential);
20 hits=differential>=0 & circshift(differential,[-1 0])<0 ;
21 hits2=differential>0 & circshift(differential,[-1 0])<=0 ;
22
23 %& XCF(1:end-1) >max(XCF)/2;
24 peaks=posiciones(hits| hits2)+1;
25 end
```

Acknowledgements

Thanks to Albert Compte, Marie Trussart and Fabrice Wendling for useful comments during the preparation of this TN.

References

- [Bikson:2004aa] M. Bikson, M. Inoue, H. Akiyama, J. K. Deans, J. E. Fox, H. Miyakawa, and J. G. Jefferys. Effects of uniform extracellular dc electric fields on excitability in rat hippocampal slices in vitro. *J Physiol*, 557(Pt 1):175–90, 2004.

Abstract: The effects of uniform steady state (DC) extracellular electric fields on neuronal excitability were characterized in rat hippocampal slices using field, intracellular and voltage-sensitive dye recordings. Small electric fields (< 40 mV mm⁻¹), applied parallel to the somato-dendritic axis, induced polarization of CA1 pyramidal cells; the relationship between applied field and induced polarization was linear (0.12 \pm 0.05 mV per mV mm⁻¹ average sensitivity at the soma). The peak amplitude and time constant (15-70 ms) of membrane polarization varied along the axis of neurons with the maximal polarization observed at the tips of basal and apical dendrites. The polarization was biphasic in the mid-apical dendrites; there was a time-dependent shift in the polarity reversal site. DC fields altered the thresholds of action potentials evoked by orthodromic stimulation, and shifted their initiation site along the apical dendrites. Large electric fields could trigger neuronal firing and epileptiform activity, and induce long-term (>1 s) changes in neuronal excitability. Electric fields perpendicular to the apical-dendritic axis did not induce somatic polarization, but did modulate orthodromic responses, indicating an effect on afferents. These results demonstrate that DC fields can modulate neuronal excitability in a time-dependent manner, with no clear threshold, as a result of interactions between neuronal compartments, the non-linear properties of the cell membrane, and effects on afferents.

11, 13

- [Bower:2003aa] James M. Bower and David Beeman. *The book of GENESIS: exploring realistic neural models with the GENeral NEural Simulation System*. Internet Edition, 2003. 3
- [Compte:2008aa] Albert Compte and et al. Spontaneous high-frequency (10 – 80 hz) oscillations during up states in the cerebral cortex in vitro. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, 28(51):13828–13844, 2008.

Abstract: High-frequency oscillations in cortical networks have been linked to a variety of cognitive and perceptual processes. They have also been recorded in small cortical slices in vitro, indicating that neuronal synchronization at these frequencies is generated in the local cortical circuit. However, in vitro experiments have hitherto necessitated exogenous pharmacological or electrical stimulation to generate robust synchronized activity in the β/γ range. Here, we demonstrate that the isolated cortical microcircuitry generates β and γ oscillations spontaneously in the absence of externally applied neuromodulators or synaptic agonists. We show this in a spontaneously active slice preparation that engages in slow oscillatory activity similar to activity during slow-wave sleep. β and γ synchronization appeared during the up states of the slow oscillation. Simultaneous intracellular and extracellular recordings revealed synchronization between the timing of incoming synaptic events and population activity. This rhythm was mechanistically similar to pharmacologically induced γ rhythms, as it also included sparse, irregular firing of neurons within the population oscillation, predominant involvement of inhibitory neurons, and a decrease of oscillation frequency after barbiturate application. Finally, we show in a computer model how a synaptic loop between excitatory and inhibitory neurons can explain the emergence of both the slow (<1 Hz) and the β -range oscillations in the neocortical network. We therefore conclude that oscillations in the β/γ range that share mechanisms with activity reported in vivo or in pharmacologically activated in vitro preparations can be generated during slow oscillatory activity in the local cortical circuit, even without exogenous pharmacological or electrical stimulation.

20

[Dayan:2001aa] Peter Dayan and L.F. Abbott. *Theoretical Neuroscience. Computational and Mathematical Modeling of Neural systems*. MIT Press, 2001. 16

[Francis:2003aa] J. T. Francis, B. J. Gluckman, and S. J. Schiff. Sensitivity of neurons to weak electric fields. *J Neurosci*, 23(19):7255–61, 2003.

Abstract: Weak electric fields modulate neuronal activity, and knowledge of the interaction threshold is important in the understanding of neuronal synchronization, in neural prosthetic design, and in the public health assessment of environmental extremely low frequency fields. Previous experimental measurements have placed the threshold between 1 and 5 mV/mm, although theory predicts that elongated neurons should have submillivolt per millimeter sensitivity near 100 microV/mm. We here provide the first experimental confirmation that neuronal networks are detectably sensitive to submillivolt per millimeter electrical fields [Gaussian pulses 26 msec full width at half-maximal, 140 microV/mm root mean square (rms), 295 microV/mm peak amplitude], an order of magnitude below previous findings, and further demonstrate that these networks are more sensitive than the average single neuron threshold (185 microV/mm rms, 394 microV/mm peak amplitude) to field modulation.

16

[Grimbert:2005aa] F. Grimbert and et al. Analysis of jansen’s model of a single cortical column. Technical Report 5597, INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE ET EN AUTOMATIQUE, June 2005. 16, 17, 19

[Jansen:1993aa] B. H. Jansen, G. Zouridakis, and M. E. Brandt. A neurophysiologically-based mathematical model of flash visual evoked potentials. *Biol Cybern*, 68(3):275–83, 1993. 16

[Jansen:1995aa] B. H. Jansen and V. G. Rit. Electroencephalogram and visual evoked potential generation in a mathematical model of coupled cortical columns. *Biol Cybern*, 73(4):357–66, 1995. 16

[Park:2005aa] E. H. Park, E. Barreto, B. J. Gluckman, S. J. Schiff, and P. So. A model of the effects of applied electric fields on neuronal synchronization. *J Comput Neurosci*, 19(1):53–70, 2005.

Abstract: We examine the effects of applied electric fields on neuronal synchronization. Two-compartment model neurons were synaptically coupled and embedded within a resistive array, thus allowing the neurons to interact both chemically and electrically. In addition, an external electric field was imposed on the array. The effects of this field were found to be nontrivial, giving rise to domains of synchrony and asynchrony as a function of the heterogeneity among the neurons. A simple phase oscillator reduction was successful in qualitatively reproducing these domains. The findings form several readily testable experimental predictions, and the model can be extended to a larger scale in which the effects of electric fields on seizure activity may be simulated.

7, 11

[Rattay:1998aa] F. Rattay. Analysis of the electrical excitation of cns neurons. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng*, 45(6):766–72, 1998.

Abstract: The artificial excitation process of neurons of the central nervous system depends on the applied extracellular field, on the geometry of the neuron and on the electrical properties of the neural subunits. Results of computer simulations are based on a compartment model of the neuron and its equivalent electrical network. Furthermore, a theory is presented which generalizes the activating function concept known from peripheral nerve stimulation. The theory predicts the influence of electrical and geometrical parameters on the excitation threshold. Generally, the myelinated axon is the part of a neuron which is most excitable to a given applied field. An example demonstrates that for a target neuron the quotient (anodic threshold current)/(cathodic threshold current) essentially depends on the position and orientation of the neuron relative to the electrode.

5

[Roth:1990aa] Bratley J. Roth and Peter J. Basser. A model of the stimulation of a nerve fiber by electromagnetic induction. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 37(6):588–597, 1990.

Abstract: A model is presented to explain the physics of nerve stimulations by electromagnetic induction. Maxwell’s equations predict the induced electric field distribution that is produced when a capacitor is discharged through a stimulating coil. A non-linear Hodgkin-Huxley cable model describes the response of the nerve fiber to this induced electric field. Once the coil’s position, orientation, and shape are given and the resistance, capacitance, and initial voltage of the stimulating circuit are specified, this model predicts the resulting transmembrane potential of the fiber as a function of distance and time. It is shown that the nerve fiber is stimulated by the gradient of the component of the induced electric field that is parallel to the fiber, which hyperpolarizes or depolarizes the membrane and may stimulate an action potential. The model predicts complicated dynamics such as action potential annihilation and dispersion.

5

[Ruffini:2008aa] Giulio Ruffini. The interaction of slowly varying electric fields with single neurons. Starlab Technical Note TN00162, Starlab Barcelona S.L., December 2008.

Abstract: This note aims to clarify several aspects of bioelectric phenomena with a focus on stimulation of a single neuron. When an electromagnetic field is coupled to a neuron, whether TMS or tDCS, the interaction is through the induced electric field and the neuron and surrounding conductive medium. We will elucidate the mechanisms for interaction and salient points to guide further work, including theoretical/numerical work with neuronal ensembles, experimental work and system design. Here we will provide:

1. A brief review of the origin of bioelectric potentials (mostly based on TN00011)
2. The derivation of the cable equation for a generic bent neuron
3. A discussion of termination boundary conditions
4. Analysis of the interaction of external fields with single neurons in steady state
5. 2D simulations in steady state
6. An analytic 1D solution with many key elements
7. An overview of neuron modeling and compartment models and how to include stimulation in them
8. A review of the state of the art in neuron electro-magnetic stimulation
9. A review of EM boundary conditions

We provide a set of conclusions for discussion.

1, 31

[Ruffini:2009aa] Giulio Ruffini. Improving focality in electromagnetic stimulation. Starlab Technical Note TN00163, Starlab Barcelona S.L., January 2009.

Abstract: As part of discussions on how to improve transcranial stimulation focality, the possibility of using bipolar configurations has been discussed, or, more generally, the use of different current or voltage sources, such as different batteries. Here we show that the combination of different current or voltage sources is a boundary value problem in conductive media, and that it therefore cannot be used to bypass the limitations associated to focality using harmonic fields. In fact, superposition of bipolar fields can be used to calculate multipolar setups as long as there are no electrode overlaps. We describe in depth the concept of harmonic fields and their relevance to electric fields in uniformly conductive media. We show that neither the sum of harmonic functions, nor the sum of squares of harmonic functions can attain local maxima outside their boundaries. Although the relevance of this to the stimulation problem is not direct, since in the brain we deal with non-conductive media, we conclude that electric field maxima will reside on the outer cortical layer. Stimulation patterns can be designed to target specific cortical regions, but with the caveat that the field maximum will occur

on the cortical surface. However, the effect of stimulation at the neuron level is not simply proportional to field strength, since neuron characteristics also play an important role in the coupling. We define the concept of “single-neuron excitation function” and provide a model for this reflecting the results of TN00162 ([Ruffini:2008aa]), namely the dependence of excitation on field intensity and relative orientation. This model can be used to couple electric field models to neuronal ensembles. We implement this excitation function into a simple single neuron model, showing it can alter the firing rate of the neuron in the expected manner. In addition, we discuss how we may target specific sets of neurons by tuning the stimulus pulse duration, since the excitation function for a given type of neuron will have a characteristic time constant. Shorter pulses than a given constant will generate limited stimulation. We discuss alternative ways to improve focality, including time and frequency stimulation control to control stimulation maps over the cortex, and also the possibility of using resonance phenomena (to be discussed in TN00164).

1, 4, 20

[Ruffini:2009ac] G. Ruffini and et al. Naf/i workshop summary: what we know, what we don’t know and next steps. Technical report, Starlab, 2009.

Abstract: The mission of the HIVE project is to research new stimulation paradigms and create a new generation of non-invasive brain stimulation technologies. Similarly, JIVE’s mission is to explore fundamental aspects of stimulation in vitro and in silico, and develop a new generation of stimulation technologies for in-vitro research. **Therefore, the tangible outputs expected from these projects are 1) new stimulation paradigms and 2) new stimulation technologies in addition to overall advancement in neuroscience modeling aspects.** In particular, stimulation technologies will focus on electric stimulation using multiple electrode system and will full control of frequencies and phases. This note provides a summary of the Neuron/Assembly field interaction (NAF/I) workshop (Barcelona, Feb 2009) conclusions, focusing on what we know, what we don’t know and what the next steps should be. The objectives of the workshop were to

- Bring together HIVE and JIVE modeling, in-vitro and in-vivo teams
- Focus on Neuron/Assembly-stimulation Field Interaction modeling and experiment
- Reach a consensus on what we know and what we don’t know about N/AFI
- Provide recommendations for theoretical and in-vitro, in-vivo experimental work
- Later on, support human experimental work and technology design

In this note we summarize the main points of this two-day event, and provide recommendations at the end. References to this work can be found in J/HIVE Starlab TNs as well as HIVE deliverables D1.1 and D3.1 (public).

11

[Trappenberg:2002aa] Thomas P. Trappenberg. *Fundamentals of Computational Neuroscience*. Oxford University Press, 2002. 6, 16, 17

[Wendling:2008aa] F Wendling and P Chauvel. *Transition to ictal activity in Temporal Lobe Epilepsy: insights from macroscopic models*. in *Computational Neuroscience in Epilepsy*, Ivan Soltesz and Kevin Staley Eds. Elsevier, 2008.

Abstract: Temporal lobe epilepsy (TLE) is one of the most common forms of partial epilepsy. It is characterized by recurrent seizures originating from one or several areas of the temporal cortex and propagating through interconnected neuronal networks within and outside the temporal lobe. Although there is current evidence that seizures are related to abnormal excessive firing and synchronization of neurons, little is known about the precise basic mechanisms underlying human epileptic seizures and mechanisms of transitions from normal to paroxysmal activity. This chapter presents some insights into transition mechanisms to ictal activity in human TLE that can be drawn from a macroscopic modeling approach that developed over the three past decades. The

term ‘macroscopic’ relates to the modeling level. Indeed, relevant variables in considered models describe the average activity of interconnected subpopulations of principal neurons and interneurons without explicit representation of mechanisms lying at the level of single cells, conversely to biologically-inspired detailed models. Although macroscopic, these models rely on neurophysiological data and have two essential features. First, their parameters relate to excitatory and inhibitory processes taking place in the considered neuronal tissue. Second, the temporal dynamics of their output is analogous to a field activity, allowing for direct comparison with real electroencephalographic signals recorded with intracerebral electrodes (depth-EEG, stereotaxic method) during presurgical evaluation of patients candidate to epilepsy surgery. The chapter provides a historical perspective about macroscopic models and describes their theoretical bases. A model-based interpretation of depth-EEG signals recorded during the transition to ictal activity is illustrated and discussed.

**Appendix B: Some key elements from the presentation performed by
Inserm during the first Hive virtual meeting (VM1, Dec. 2008).**

HYPER
INTERACTION
VIABILITY
EXPERIMENTS

Virtual Meeting Dec. 17, 2008

Draft report

Literature review and preliminary results about neurophysiological models of brain activity

Behnam Molaee Ardekani

Isabelle Merlet

Fabrice Wendling

Laboratoire Traitement du Signal et de L'Image
INSERM U642 - UNIVERSITE DE RENNES 1
Campus de Beaulieu
35042 Rennes Cedex - France -
Tel : (33) 2 23 23 56 05 ou (33) 2 23 23 62 20
Fax : (33) 2 23 23 69 17
[Skype pseudo: fabwenrennes](#)

HIVE's main goal

“To interact with the brain through noninvasive stimulation”

- The Brain
 - A highly complex nonlinear dynamical system
 - Changes in the dynamics of this system \leftrightarrow changes in brain activity
 - Brain activity is characterized by oscillations at local and global level
 - Changes in the dynamics reflect in electrophysiological signals (depth or scalp EEG in humans, LFPs in animal models) as transitions between oscillations
- “Interacting with the brain” = being able to induce a **transition** from one type of **brain dynamics** to another in response to a **stimulation** protocol that we **have designed**.
This includes the possible “restoration” of missing waves in diseased patients
- If we can induce such transitions, this would constitute a proof of concept for future developments in machine to brain communication

Question:

How, where and when should we stimulate to induce such transitions?

To answer this question, we can

- Develop a model of the brain activity and the resulting EEG
- Study the changes in the EEG in response to stimulation (tDCS, TMS)
- Make predictions from the model
- Verify experimentally

However, these are general and very (maybe too) ambitious goals

The first step could be:

- To focus on a very common transition: Background EEG (BKG) \leftrightarrow alpha-like activity (alpha-waves or spindles)
 - Alpha-waves occur by eye closing or in the first stage of sleep.
 - Spindles occur during sleep (beginning of stage 2)
- This transition can be easily observed on the scalp EEG

Literature review on related topics

Studies about changes in **alpha-like** activity induced by external stimulation

- Magnetic exposure influences human EEG activity (Cook et al. 2002 review).
One of the most consistent results is a “*higher resting and evoked EEG **alpha** (8–13 Hz) activity*” subsequent to LF MFs exposure (Bell et al. 1992, 1994 , Lyskov et al. 1993ab, Cook et al. 2004)
- Cvetkovic, D.; Jovanov, E.; Cosic, I. Alterations in Human EEG Activity Caused by Extremely Low Frequency Electromagnetic Fields Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society, 2006.
*33 subjects double blind counter balanced. Duration of stim : 1 min – 1 min no stim, Double coils over the head. Frequency : 50, 16,7, 13, 10, 8,3, 4 Hz (flux density 20 mT). Results : significant increase in **alpha1**, **alpha2**, beta1 in frontal regions, significant decrease in **alpha2** band in parietal region and occipital region*
- Sergio Ghione, Cristina Del Seppia, Lorena Mezzasalma, Luca Bonfiglio, Effects of 50 Hz electromagnetic fields on electroencephalographic **alpha** activity, dental pain threshold and cardiovascular parameters in humans, Neuroscience Letters 382 (2005) 112–117
*“80 mT magnetic treatment : **Alpha** activity almost doubled compared to sham treatment”*
- Kaspar Schindler, Thomas Nyffeler, Roland Wiest, Martinus Hauf, et al., Theta burst transcranial magnetic stimulation is associated with increased EEG synchronization in the stimulated relative to unstimulated cerebral hemisphere, Neuroscience Letters 436 (2008) 31–34. *“Synchronization was computed for broadband EEG and for the delta, theta, **alpha**, beta and gamma frequency bands”*.
- M.J. Schroeder, R.E. Barr, Quantitative analysis of the electroencephalogram during cranial electrotherapy stimulation, Clinical Neurophysiology 112 (2001) 2075–2083. *“CES caused the **alpha** band mean frequency to shift downward”*.
- Wolfgang Klimesch, Paul Sauseng and Christian Gerloff, Enhancing cognitive performance with repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation at human individual alpha frequency, European Journal of Neuroscience Volume 17 Issue 5, 2003, 1129 - 1133 *“Results : IAF + 1 Hz enhances task performance + concomitantly, the extent of task-related **alpha** desynchronization”*
- (*) Please, see “Appendix 1:Thalamo-cortical circuits and alpha-like activity (from slide #38) for review on alpha activity (independently from stimulation).

WP1: Biophysical models of stimulation

In this context, WP1 could start with dealing with the following questions:

- Can we simulate background EEG and alpha-like activity from a “plausible” model of the brain?
- Can we identify, from this model, the “essential” parameter modifications that induce changes from BKG to alpha-like ?
- Can we induce such modifications by applying appropriate electrical fields?
- Then, how can we alter alpha-like activity by stimulation?

What is a “plausible model of the brain”?

Such a model should:

- Be constructed based on neurophysiological as well as neuroanatomical data (especially those relating to “specific” waves, like alpha-like oscillations).
- Take into account the distribution of stimulation currents in the head and resulting electrical fields at the level of neuronal tissue
- Be able to generate a multi-channel EEG (output of the model)
 - Required for development & validation the model (comparison with real EEG recordings)
 - Required in the simulation studies of the effects of stimulation
 - Required to predict which stimulations parameters (time, space) are the most likely to induce transitions of dynamics.

Plausible model: required features

- 1) Neocortical areas (« patches ») with realistic anatomy
- 2) Coupled populations of neurons inside each patch → local activity and LFPs
- 3) Connectivity patterns at local level (within patches)
- 4) Connectivity patterns global level (between patches)
- 5) Forward problem to compute the simulated EEG (dipole theory)
- 6) Effects of applied electrical fields

STEP1 → STEP2 → STEP3 → STEP4

Recording conditions
Ex: awake, relaxing, sleep, level of alertness

Real EEG
BKG ↔ alpha
Depth, surface

Patient
Real brain

Recordings

Comparison
Signal processing
(Spectral, morphological & spatial features)

Parameter fitting

Simulated EEG
BKG ↔ alpha
Depth, surface

Simulation
(forward solution)

Model
(Macro., nonlinear dynamical System)

Stim. params.
~~Where, when,~~
how?

Non-invasive Stimulation
Electrical field $E(t,X)$

Physiology
(Neuronal pops, local and global connectivity)

Anatomy
(main brain areas, cocomac project)

Experimental data
(in vivo measurments)

THE HIVE PROJECT - HYPER INTERACTION VIABILITY EXPERIMENTS

Could computers someday interact directly with the human brain? In the next 50 years we will witness the coming of age of technologies for fluent brain-computer and computer-mediated brain-to-brain interaction. While recent research has delivered important breakthroughs in brain-to-computer transmission, little has been achieved in the other direction – computer-controlled brain stimulation. HIVE is a FET Open FP7 EU project. Our goal is to research stimulation paradigms to design, develop and test a new generation of more powerful and controllable non-invasive brain stimulation technologies. HIVE will develop improved electrical current distribution and multi-scale neuron-current interaction models and carry out stimulation experiments using tDCS, TMS, EEG and fMRI in different scenarios, and based on these develop multisite transcranial current stimulation technologies implementing real time EEG monitoring and feedback. HIVE will also explore high-level communication using stimulation, stimulation during different states of consciousness, stimulation and therapy, as well as 'sense synthesis', that is, the construction of new perceptions deriving from sensors interacting directly with brains through stimulation systems – all with the goal of probing the limits of non-invasive computer-to-brain interfaces. We believe that given the fundamental role of interaction in human experience, advances in this area can deliver breakthrough technologies of great value in addition to advancing the state-of-the-art in fundamental neuroscience research and neurology.

hiVE
HYPER
INTERACTION
VIABILITY
EXPERIMENTS

PRODUCED BY:

Starlab
Living Science

HIVE [2008-2012] is funded by the European Commission and coordinated by Starlab under the Future Emerging Technologies (FET) - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) program nursery of novel and emerging scientific ideas.

Consortium: Starlab Barcelona (coordinator), Charité U. Berlin, Bangor U., Kapodistrian U. of Athens, U. of Lisbon, INSERM and U. Pablo de Olavide.

Coordinator: Giulio Ruffini (giulio.ruffini@starlab.es)

EU Project Officer: Aymard de Touzalin

<http://hive-eu.org>

The project HIVE acknowledges the financial support of the Future and Emerging Technologies (FET) programme within the Seventh Framework Programme for Research of the European Commission, under FET-Open grant number: 222079